

A DISSERTATION ON

**A STUDY OF MICRO FINANCING AND
SELF-HELP GROUPS**

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TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that the project report titled “A STUDY OF MICRO FINANCING AND SELF-HELP GROUPS” carried out by Ms. Monika Marwaha D/o Sh. Ravinder Marwaha has been accomplished under my guidance and supervision as a duly registered M. Phil student of Department of Commerce, University Centre for Distance Learning, Chaudhary Devi Lal University, Sirsa. This dissertation is being submitted by her in the partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of Degree of M. Phil in Commerce from Chaudhary Devi Lal University, Sirsa.

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DECLARATION

I, Monika Marwaha, hereby declare that the work presented in the report titled “A STUDY OF MICRO FINANCING AND SELF-HELP GROUPS” is the genuine work done originally by me and has not been published or submitted elsewhere for the requirement of the degree programme. Any literature, data or works done by others and cited within this dissertation has been given due acknowledgement and listed in the reference section.

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

“Micro-credit is something which is not going to disappear... because this is a need of the people, whatever name you give it, you have to have those financial facilities coming to them because it is totally unfair... to deny half the population of the world financial services”

-Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Founder - Bangladesh Grameen Bank, in March 2002¹

Micro finance refers to the provision of financial services to low-income clients for the business and other personal needs. It addresses a full range of banking needs for poor people. More broadly, it refers to a movement that envisions a world in which as many poor and near-poor households as possible have permanent access to an appropriate range of high quality financial services, including not just credit but also savings, insurance, and fund transfers.² Those who promote micro finance generally believe that such access will help poor people to get rid of poverty. Micro Financing includes a variety of services other than just credit e.g. housing, stock and variety of insurance, training and supervision etc. where insurance is wider based on the requirement of the poor i.e. health insurance, live stock insurance, price derivatives and options, weather insurance covering the risk of weather, improper cultivation practices, price, policy, pests and diseases etc. Thus the activities in micro financing has been categorised as Microcredit, Micro Savings, Micro insurance and Remittances.

In Stuart Rutherford’s recent book *The Poor and Their Money*, several types of needs are cited e.g. Lifecycle Needs, Personal Emergencies needs, Disasters needs and Investment Opportunities. Poor people find creative and often collaborative ways to meet these needs, primarily through creating and exchanging different forms of non-cash value. Common substitutes for cash vary from country to country but typically include livestock, grains, jewellery and precious metals. According to a 1995 World Bank estimate, in most developing countries the formal financial system reaches only the top 25% of the economically active

¹ Grameen Bank in 'strongest position ever', www.news.bbc.co.uk, Available at <http://www.icmrindia.org/free%20resources/casestudies/Bangladesh%20Grameen%20Bank1.htm>, accessed on March 12, 2002

² <http://profile.iiita.ac.in/IMB2008005/Microfinance.pdf>

population - the bottom 75% have no access to financial services apart from moneylenders (**Kalavathi and Villalan, 2008**). Vijay Mahajan, Managing Director of BASICS (Basic Support for Institutionalizing Child Survival), estimated that 90 million farm holdings, 30 million non-agricultural enterprises and 50 million landless households in India collectively need approx US\$30 billion credit annually. This is about 5% of India's GDP and does not seem an unreasonable estimate (**Arora, 2005**). A World Bank study assessing access to financial institutions found that amongst rural households in Andhra Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh, 59% lack access to deposit account and 78% lack access to credit. Many of business management gurus have suggested the need for any type organizations to learn and be adaptive with environment as they grow and expand (**Hartungi, 2007**). Muhammad Yunus suggested that in Bangladesh 80% of the poor are covered under microfinance. The remaining 20% are expected to be covered with in next two years. India has been able to cover only 20% people under it and needs to be speed up (**Sharma, 2009**). The Micro banking Bulletin (July, 2003) reports that the institutions that reach out mainly to poor clients incurred operational expenses, that were, on average about 60 percent of the total loan amount given. Personal expenses made just under half of that (**Noponen, 2005**). India has the huge population under the poverty line which requires the direct measures for their financial inclusion in order to provide the equal opportunity to grow. The poverty and the indebtedness are the main cause for the agrarian distress. Various schemes are announced by the Government from time to time but these acted as the short term remedies and proved to be the relief for those only who have borrowed from the bank and not to those who are trapped in the clutches of the money lenders. Over the past centuries practical visionaries from the Franciscan monks who founded the community-oriented pawnshops of the fifteenth century, to the founders of the European credit union movement in the nineteenth century (such as Friedrich Wilhelm Raiffeisen) and the founders of the microcredit movement in the 1970s (such as Muhammad Yunus) have tested practices and built institutions designed to bring the kinds of livelihood opportunities and risk management tools that financial services provide to the doorsteps of poor people.³ The success of Grameen Bank has exemplified the success of the micro financing in world. But the other developing countries are finding it difficult to attain the equivalent success factor. In nations with lower population densities, meeting the operating costs of a retail branch by serving nearby customers has proven considerably more challenging.

³ <http://microfinance.cfsites.org/custom.php?pageid=30254>, accessed on 31st January, 2010.

Microfinance has been growing rapidly with \$25B currently at work in microfinance loans. It is estimated that the industry needs \$250 billion to get capital to all the poor people who need it.⁴

The lack of full coverage in the current system has generated the need for an innovative system for the financially uncovered population of India. Almost all the governments came up with the number of lucrative schemes full of great packages of grants and subsidies for poverty alleviation. Though the purpose may be to attract the vote bank but there were continuous efforts as far as all the political parties are concerned. The research has proved that these mandatory programs implemented through banking infrastructure has never been interpreted by the banks as the profitable and the commercial activity and thus never been encouraged. Through the determined efforts, the government of India is able to expand the formal credit base to the rural poor tremendously but it is infeasible to expect from the banks, possessing the limited resources, to manage the large number of the customer base with the smaller credit needs, frequent and urgent demands accompanied by almost zero collaterals to offer. The system of lending through Self help groups (SHGs) has emerged as the innovative tool to provide the profitable business to banks as well as credit to the weaker section of the society. Financial exclusion is increasingly being recognised as an important aspect of socio-economic inequality where disadvantaged individuals and communities are isolated from mainstream financial services, particularly affordable and readily available credit. In the face of these problems, social policy initiatives have emerged that have travelled under various names: social investment, micro-finance, community finance and community development finance. These initiatives are seen as the basis of a 'new economics' that will create self-sustaining local economies. The government is promoting such community development finance as an aspect of community regeneration with the aim of providing credit to poor communities to stimulate local enterprise and thereby reduce dependency on state support. The same approach is being taken to grant-funded community and voluntary organisations to encourage them into a neo-market approach to the delivery of services (**Affleck & Mellor, 2006**). The Institutional Framework for financing at the micro level is two-fold. Firstly it is the informal financial service providers (moneylenders, pawnbrokers, savings collectors, money-guards and input supply shops) and secondly it is the Member-owned organizations (Self-Help Groups, credit unions, and a variety of hybrid organizations like financial service associations). Various micro credit facilitators are

⁴ http://www.bukisa.com/articles/106425_business-finance-the-releam-of-microfinance

Domestic Commercial Banks, Public Sector Banks, Private Sector Banks, Local Area Banks, Regional Rural Banks, Co-operative Banks, Co-operative Societies, Registered NBFCs, Unregistered NBFCs and Other providers like Societies, Trusts etc. The combined unidirectional approach of all the providers can make the dream possible of self independent India where the balanced regional growth can be ensured.

Self Help Groups are usually formed by women from the rural areas for pooling their savings and giving loans to members of the groups. National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development has played a very significant role in supporting group formation, linking them with banks as also promoting best practices. The Self Help Group is given loan against the group guarantee. It is ensured that the credit is provided at the reasonable rates of interest, sufficient loans in the smaller dimensions in comparatively higher frequencies either for smoothening of the consumption pattern of the poor families or funding the small scale business propositions. The people are benefited by the concept of Micro Financing by forming the Self Help Groups even with the number of ten members. Maximum membership allowed is twenty. There are three office bearers of the group namely president, secretary and cashier holding all the affairs beginning with the monthly deposits collection to the disbursement of the loans to its members. The president is the main office bearer who controls all the affairs like arranging the monthly meetings, depositing the monthly deposits into the bank account, condemning any group member who is violating the provisions of the group etc. Secretary is the second authority who assists the president and acts in the absence of the latter. The cashier takes into account all the affairs related with cash i.e. statement of collections and the statement of the disbursement made to the members in form of loans. Joining an existing SHG at the later stage is often a costly affair for an aspiring villager. In order to maintain parity among the members a new member has to join by depositing the total accumulated individual savings and interest of the group. Thus it is often easier for a person not affiliated with an SHG to start a new SHG than joining a pre-existing one.

Institutions offering micro-credit are usually non-governmental organisations (NGOs), but can also be credit unions, specialised banks or even commercial banks. Lending methods may vary from country to country and institution to institution, but the general framework comprises a collateral-free lending model with reasonable rates of interest. “Reasonable” in this case may generally mean a little more than that charged by urban

commercial banks because door-step transaction costs are higher (the bank comes to the villager, not the villager to the bank) but certainly not anywhere near that charged by local money-lenders. Although the loans are made out individually, they are handed out to small groups of persons, known as “peer groups”, and if one person fails to repay, the entire group is penalised. This “social collateral” frees the borrower from complicated legal procedures and at the same time ensures repayment, which indeed is very high, almost 95 per cent. The loan cycle is also much shorter than commercial bank loans, rarely exceeding one year, and repayment is usually done in a weekly or fortnightly cycle, so that the borrower is not burdened with large dues.

The borrowers utilize this loan to set up or to boost already-existing independent small scale units, which could be something as simple as a roadside shop. In some cases, micro-credit is also given for housing purposes. Not burdened with high interest rates and due to the friendly repayment terms, almost all borrowers are able to repay their loans on time and at the same time prosper in their enterprise. Once a loan cycle is over, a person can take further loans. This led to a search for alternative policies, systems and procedures, saving and loan products, other complementary services and new delivery mechanisms that would fulfill the requirements of the poor. It is in this context that micro credit has emerged as the most suitable and practical alternative to the conventional banking in reaching the hitherto unreached poor population.

In the history of India, various MFIs and NGOs dedicated to financial inclusion in the economy have emerged over the time. Many of them are initiated by the real beneficiaries in the system for the welfare of their own members by lending the deposits accumulated by them at the concessional rates of interest, without security and for longer duration of time. SHARE, BASIX and SEWA are the few names which are landmarks in the system. SKS India, launched in 1998, is the one of the fastest growing micro finance institution in the world. It has provided over Rs 6,212 crore and having maintained loans outstanding Rs. 2,216 crore to 3,906,007 women members in the poor regions of the country. Per month they are adding 2.5 million customers & are targeting 15 million customers by the end of the financial year 2012. In terms of growth the rate is 200% **(Ravindranath, 2009)**. Spandana founded in 1998 is also one of the fastest expanding MFI in the country. It has also proved its efficiency with the operating expense ratio of 5.5% on the portfolio. It now boasts of the client base which consists of almost 1.5% of the BPL population of the India **(Ravindranath, 2009)**. Another initiative is SEWA which is a trade union of the poor women workers registered in 1972. Initially it provided the financial &

social security to women laborers in the state of Gujarat. But now it is registered as a national union with seven sister SEWAs constituting its membership. These are SEWA Madhya Pradesh, SEWA Bihar, SEWA Uttar Pradesh, SEWA Delhi, SEWA Rajasthan and SEWA Kerala. In addition, SEWA has helped or is associated with workers' movements in other countries. Bandhan, based in West Bengal, is started as a Capacity Building Institution (CBI) in November 2000 & opened its first microfinance branch at Bagnan in Howrah district of West Bengal in July 2002. There are various recent landmarks also setting the latest examples in the field of micro financing. Membership of Sa-Dhan (a leading association) has expanded from 43 to 96 Community Development Finance Institutions during 2001-04. The outreach of SHARE Microfinance Limited, for instance, grew from 1,875 to 86,905 members between 2000 and 2005 and its loan portfolio has grown from US\$0.47 million to US\$40 million (**Arora, 2009**).

Micro finance is the provision of a broad range of financial services such as deposits, loans, payments, money transfers, and insurance to the low-income households and their micro enterprises. The basic purpose of micro finance is to provide access to financial assistance, including credit to the poor to enable them to start/expand micro enterprises to break out of poverty. Micro credit enables the poor people to be thrifty and helps them in availing the credit and other financial services for improving their income and living standards.

In India, the bill for the regulation of MFIs is pending in Parliament since 2007. The bill seeks to promote and regulate MFOs (Micro Finance Organisations) and designates NABARD as the regulator for the sector. Mandatory regular reporting by all MFOs will help in building the robust database for the sector. The proposed legislation has been pending on the various key issues such as the exclusion of NBFCs from the preview of MFOs, lowering the interest rates, limited product range (excluding insurance and pension etc.), no limit for the deposits to be accepted by MFOs and NABARD being the regulator. The bill, reframed as Micro Financial Sector (Development and Regulation) Bill, 2009, is waiting for its fate to be decided in the coming 14th Lok Sabha session.

One of the schemes offered for the development of the poor population in India is SGSY (Swarnjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojna). According to the SGSY Guidelines, "The Self help group approach helps the poor to build their self-confidence through community action. The interaction in group meetings and collective decision making enable them in identification and prioritization of their needs and resources. This process would ultimately lead to the

strengthening and socio-economic empowerment of the rural poor as well as improve their collective bargaining power.”⁵ The SGSY strategy includes identifying a cluster of activities at the block level and funding Self help groups to perform these activities. The programme is implemented countrywide through a hierarchy of SGSY committees, at the central, state, district and block levels. The actual implementation requires close interaction between the government officials at various levels, particularly the DRDAs (District Rural Development Agencies), managers from the participating banks, NABARD, as well as NGOs. The actual disbursement of government funds would be through the DRDAs who would distribute the subsidy to banks. The programme recognizes the important role that NGOs play in the formation and nurturing of Self-Help Groups and seeks to include them in the exercise. As per **Ghatak (1999)**, the key is that group-lending schemes provide incentives for similar types to group together. This process can be instrumental in improving repayment rates, allowing for lower interest rates, and raising social welfare. The group- lending contract provides a way to price discriminate that is impossible with an individual-lending contract (**Morduch, 1999**). From the point of view of Self help groups, SGSY is an excellent source of subsidized credit. If a group survives for 6 months it becomes eligible for a revolving fund of Rs. 25,000 from a participating bank. Out of this loan, Rs. 10,000 is in the form of government subsidy and banks may charge interest only the amount exceeding this Rs. 10,000. The Rs. 25,000 fund injection becomes part of the group corpus. With some exceptions, six months after the receipt of the revolving fund the groups would be tested for their preparedness to take up economic activities. If they pass the test, they would be eligible for loan-and-subsidy for economic activity up to a maximum of Rs. 10,000 per group member or Rs. 1.25 lakhs per group, whichever is less. There are also incentives, payable in several stages, to NGOs or “animators” incubating and nurturing Self help groups.

There are still serious demand-supply imbalances, limited involvement of commercial banks, small size of microfinance institutions (MFIs), minuscule outreach of MFIs in terms of the proportion of poor households served, covering less than 5 percent of India's rural poor and extremely skewed distribution across states. Further, the scope of Indian MFIs continues to be extremely narrow with only India's three top MFIs offering composite services (**Hossein, Redfern, and Carothers, 2006**). As per years Microcredit Summit Report 1997, a

⁵ Swarnjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana Guidelines issued by Government of India, Ministry of Rural Development,

high profile consortium of policymakers, charitable foundations, and practitioners started a drive to raise over \$20 billion for microfinance start-ups in the next ten years (**Morduch, 1999**). Despite credit linkage of more than 1 million Self help groups and mobilization of about Rs. 3000 crores as credit from the formal financial institutions, Micro Financing still forms a small proportion of the total bank credit in India.

Rationale behind Micro Financing

Micro financing has established a 'win-win' proposition for all the parties concerned in the business. On one hand, Government is successful in establishing the social balance by providing an independent life to the poor in the villages who are always under the shadow of scarcity of the resources and on the other hand, banks are achieving their market targets by widening their customer base in association with MFIs and NGOs who are again able to meet their objective of ensuring the equal financial opportunities to the poor. Micro financing has provided the cheaper finance to the poor. The bottom section of the society who was exploited by the moneylenders in the region is served by the mechanism of micro financing. The reasonable interest rates with zero collateral have invited the even poorest families to invest in the viable business opportunities which could help them to get out of the clutches of the poverty and forceful starvations. Microfinance has drawn attention to bottom-lined borrowers especially the women who had been poorly served by the formal financial sector since the days of independence. This has led to the increase in the physical and mental independence among the male-dominated weaker section of the society. MFIs consist of Refinance Institutions, Banks, Non Government Organisations and Self help groups dealing with small loans and deposits in rural, semi urban or urban areas enabling people to raise savings, productive investments and thereby their standard of living (**Nadarajan and Ponmurugan, 2006**). The products are designed as per the personal needs of the region under coverage.

It generates jobs and self-employment to many. This is the right time for the micro finance movement in India. It can be an answer to the critical situation resulted by financial crisis. For the overall growth of the country, rural India is required to be facilitated with the resources scarce at their disposal and Micro financing is ensuring that much required financial coverage. The financial sector has been improving with the parallel improvement in the

standard of living of the people below poverty line by increased level of savings and investment in the economy and the reduction in the level of unemployment. Micro financing is emerging as the panacea for prevailing social evils in India. In Bangladesh, the students were given loans, most of which have opted to become entrepreneurs after they completed their studies. Interest free loans of 1000 Taka were given to 1,00,000 beggars, 15000 of which has stopped begging and small business.

Another booster for the development is the group lending. Financing through Self help groups reduces transaction costs for both lenders and borrowers. While lenders have to handle only a single Self help group account instead of a large number of small-sized individual accounts and the borrower is relieved of the expenses of traveling, burden of paper work and loss of effective workdays because it is divided among the group members.

The people are benefited by the concept of Micro Financing by forming the Self help groups. All the transactions are performed jointly by that group. Even with ten members the group can be started. Maximum membership allowed is twenty. There are three office bearers of the group namely president, secretary and cashier holding all the affairs starting from the collection of monthly installments to the payment of the loans to the members. The president is the main office bearer who controls all the affairs like arranging the monthly meetings, depositing the monthly deposits into the bank account, condemning any group member who is violating the provisions of the group etc. Secretary is the second authority who assists the president and acts in the absence of the latter. The cashier takes into account all the affairs related with cash i.e. statement of collections and the statement of the disbursement made to the members in form of loans. Joining an existing Self help group is often a costly affair for an aspiring villager. In order to maintain parity among the members a new member has to join by depositing the total accumulated individual savings and interest of the group. Thus it is often easier for a person not affiliated with Self help group to start a new Self help group than joining a pre-existing one. The programs point to innovations like “group-lending” contracts and new attitudes about subsidies as the keys to their successes. Group-lending contracts effectively make a borrower’s neighbours co-signers to loans, mitigating problems created by informational asymmetries between lender and borrower. Neighbours now have incentives to monitor each other and to exclude risky borrowers from participation, promoting repayments even in the absence of collateral requirements (**Morduch, 1999**).

The institutions offering micro-credit are usually non-governmental organisations (NGOs), but can also be credit unions, specialised banks or even commercial banks. Lending methods may vary from country to country and institution to institution, but the general framework comprises a collateral-free lending model with reasonable rates of interest. “Reasonable” in this case may generally mean a little more than that charged by urban commercial banks because door-step transaction costs are higher but certainly not anywhere near that charged by local money-lenders. Although the loans are made out individually, they are handed out to small groups of persons, known as “peer groups”, and if one person fails to repay, the entire group is penalised. This “social collateral” frees the borrower from complicated legal procedures and at the same time ensures repayment, which indeed is very high, almost 99 per cent (concluded by literature and supported by the current survey). The loan cycle is also much shorter than commercial bank loans, rarely exceeding one year, and repayment is usually done in a weekly or fortnightly cycle, so that the borrower is not burdened with large dues. The borrowers utilize this loan to set up or to boost already-existing independent small scale units, which could be something as simple as a roadside shop. Not burdened with high interest rates and due to the friendly repayment terms, almost all borrowers are able to repay their loans on time and at the same time prosper in their enterprise. Once a loan cycle is over, a person can take further loans. This led to a search for alternative policies, systems and procedures, saving and loan products, other complementary services and new delivery mechanisms that would fulfill the requirements of the poor. It is in this context that micro credit has emerged as the most suitable and practical alternative to the conventional banking in reaching the hitherto unreached poor population. The basic purpose of micro finance is to provide access to financial assistance, including credit to the poor to enable them to start/expand micro enterprises to break out of poverty. Micro credit enables the poor people to be thrifty and helps them in availing the credit and other financial services for improving their income and living standards.

A new term has been introduced in the budget this year. The “debt swap” would strengthen income retention in the hands of the poor who had borrowed on disadvantageous terms for their emergent requirements. This would also help those who had mortgaged their small holdings for obtaining such loans to redeem their lands. The other major initiative announced was the coverage of all Self help group members by LIC with the Janshree Bhima Jojana for insuring life and disability. The National Health Insurance Scheme would cover all

workers in the unorganised sector. They would get a cover of Rs. 30,000 towards treatment of illness and hospitalisation.

Bandhan is ranked 2nd among all MFIs globally by Forbes (and 1st in India) followed by Microcredit Foundation of India at 13th rank. Out of the total 50 institutes, India bags seven positions out of them.⁶

⁶ http://www.google.co.in/search?hl=en&q=BANDhan+forbes&meta=&aq=f&aqi=&aql=&oq=&gs_rfai=, accessed on 12th March, 2010.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The concept of micro financing does not hold the deep-rooted historical tails due to its recent emergence, at least, in the Indian economy. It started taking its practical shape long after the financial experts and social workers are able to facilitate the poor masses to understand its conceptual base and develop the financial faith in the system. The academicians and students recognised the importance of the mechanism but failed to find the suitable literature on the same. Therefore, even in the presence of several hundred research papers; students, researchers, and practitioners needed something more accessible and handy that provided a thorough understanding of the basic concepts, as well as extensive information about this growing development strategy (**Chatterjee and Sarangi, 2006**). The researchers had explored the different dimensions of micro financing over the years. The aim of the research is basically to evaluate the present market scenario and explore the future potential for the growth in the selected regions in the world. Each research attempt aims at concluding and guiding the policy makers in the practical future decisions. The effectiveness of the system has been evaluated by the researchers by judging the role of Government policies and welfare schemes initiated from time to time and the initiatives and support lent by the network of commercial banks in the region. The microfinance revolution, particularly the success stories of institutions like Grameen Bank in Bangladesh, Banco Sol in Bolivia, and Bank Rakyat in Indonesia, attracted several economists to study microfinance in the latter half of the 1990s. However, for undergraduate and graduate students of economics, public policy, and development studies, there was a nagging problem—the plethora of mechanisms and institutions that fell under the label of microfinance were varied and complex, and there was no accessible source that presented all the material coherently (**Chatterjee and Sarangi, 2006**). The contracts have caught the attention of economic theorists, and they have brought global recognition to the group-lending model of Bangladesh's Grameen Bank (**Morduch, 1999**).

The system of micro financing is complex in terms of developing and exploring the basic structure. The evaluation part is equally complicated due to the two types of limitations. Firstly, in respect of the designing the strategies to study the extent of existence in the far-flung areas and the impact on the people who are not enough qualified to understand the

methodology and the eligibility for the various schemes instituted for the growth of the sector. Secondly, the data collection is the tedious task to judge effectiveness and to evaluate the machinery in the system. The success rate determination of the system is confined to the distinct areas and concerned with the uneducated and disadvantaged section of the society with no exposure to the real commercial world. The facts on the papers may not reflect the actual face of the society. The records generated at the Government offices and bank branches claiming the success stories may not be backed by the real gainers in the villages. Research is being conducted qualitatively with the support of the quantitative data available in the Government and NGOs records. Various methods have been adopted for the collection of the qualitative and the quantitative data ranging from the secondary data analysed over the countries to the primary data obtained by interviewing the persons engaged in the machinery either the borrowers or the lenders. Most of the research papers have set the overview of the market as their primary objective subject to its qualitative interpretation for the conclusive results **(Cornelis and ruben, 2008)**. There are different data sources explored for the effective research in the area due to the availability of variety of information stored at different locations to be explored and analysed to conclude. For collection of primary data **Azad, Shamsuddoha and Hayder Arif (2004)** had used direct interview method. Two sets of interview schedules have been prepared, first set is for executives of the selected micro finance agencies and the second set for the loanees. The data and information collected from primary and secondary sources have been analyzed using the statistical tools like average, percentage, and parametric and non-parametric tests have been used as and when required. By way of in depth interviews to semi-structured interview conducted in the rural areas of Indonesia, the factor contributing to the success of BRI (Bank Rakyat Indonesia) are concluded to guide the newly designed programs in the different countries **(Hartungi R., 2007)**.

Various research papers came out over the years which have presented the overview of the existence of micro financing in the different countries. They have presented the strategies being followed in their respective regions and highlighted the limitations in the success. For highlighting the number of problems acting as the hindrance in the development of the sector and suggesting the remedies for the same, the case studies method is being followed. The analysis was performed to judge the effect of the micro financing for eliminating poverty. The conceptual strategies are developed to guide the micro financing programs to get

very effective (**Mayoux, 1999**). The researchers tried to adopt the statistical tools to facilitate the evaluation of the innovative options experimented in micro financing to give weightage to the conclusions drawn under their research. Through questionnaires, cross-sectional survey conducted in Nigeria was evaluated by t-statistic. The financial and other outreach performance of MFIs has been analysed and found discouraging in Nigeria (**Emeni, 2008**). The risks associated with the micro financing business are studied and recommendations are suggested on the basis of the financial statements of the different MFs studied together (**Greuning, Gallardo, and Randhawa, Dec, 1998**). Microfinance is relatively a recent experiment against poverty alleviation in developing countries. Originally it started as a new institutional strategy to fill the gap between supply and demand for credit by the poor. The research has always targeted to develop this system as the growth-oriented tool. For the purpose, the researchers tried to find out the gaps in the implementation by analysing the region specific problems. The delivering of credit services to the poor either for smoothening of consumption or for the income generating activities is called a 'minimalist approach' in microfinance. The major objective of this approach is to solve the problem of unemployment in general and micro enterprise development in particular by supplying financial products. But, over the years it has been realized that this approach has failed in unleashing the micro entrepreneurship among the poor. Hence, as an alternative, the microfinance sector should be redesigned in such a way that it delivers both financial and non-financial services to the poor. In this line of thought the research attempts to present the new paradigm for the development of micro enterprises through microfinance within the framework of 'maximalist approach'. The empirical study of maximalist approach shows that microfinance will be a true lubricant for micro enterprise development only when the finance flows with the non-financial services, which have a greater positive impact on the livelihood of the poor (**Shetty, 2008**). The research has demonstrated the complete product range and set certain new recommendations for the new entrants in different market areas (**Cornelis and Ruben, 2008**).

A variety of models and strategies for micro financing have been adopted by the different practitioners in the world with the varying role of all the parties and the different levels of regional coverage. (1) Linkage Model (General Model): This model is the basic and traditional one facilitating the savings of the group members through Self help group. These savings are kept under the safe custody of the bank. The credit is provided by the bank at the

rates decided by the respective bank. (2) Modified Linkage Model: The savings are made with Self help group by the group members on the monthly basis and the savings in turn are made with bank. Bank provides the credit to the individual members at the rates prescribed by the bank in the proportion decided by the officials. (3) NGO Model: This model has the variation over the previous model in the respect that the services provided by the banks to the Self help groups are facilitated and linked through the network of NGOs generally at the regional level. All the support and linkage services are availed of by Self help groups for selecting the appropriate credit needs, evaluating the banks, obtaining the credit and ensuring the proper allocation of the borrowed money. (4) Modified NGO Model: The members pool their savings to Self help group account followed by NGO which is in the direct contact with the bank which can finance Self help group through NGO itself. (5) Indirect NGO Model: The model differs in the respect that sometimes NGOs are operating at the root level. They recruit the rural population of the respective region for their business operations. (6) IFAD Model: This model is inspired by International Fund for Agricultural Development. The mechanism is supported and monitored by the department of the specifically assigned the task of micro financing development. (7) SGSY (Swaranjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana) Model: Under the model, DRDA (District Rural Development Agency) is the agency responsible for growth of micro financing in the nation. For the purpose, it is guiding and monitoring board among all the associated parties at all the stages. (8) SHPI Model: Self Help Promoting Institutions (with NABARD assistance) is the unique feature in the system for providing support and linkage services which are provided by NGOs in other models. Dedicated to improving the lot of the poor in developing countries, these micro lending NGOs began serving microenterprises in the 1980s, responding to the critical income and employment opportunities of their urban and rural clientele. Today some leading NGOs have created financial methodologies that serve increasing numbers of the poor and generate repayment rates that compare favorably with the loan performance of many traditional commercial banks. By using these methodologies, NGOs have achieved increasing levels of sustainability, even to the point of outright profits without subsidies (**Christen, 1997**). A model framework for understanding the relationships between the factors affecting outreach performance in Indian RRBs is developed. The attitudes and behaviours of managers, along with institutional characteristics, are identified as influences on market orientation, service innovation, customer satisfaction and outreach performance within

RRBs. The product focused approach rather than market oriented strategy is the major reason for the slow progress in the Indian financial sector. There is a long list of the arguments for the micro credit campaigns over the countries claiming to ensure the success in terms of the deeper reach to the sections of the society untouched by the normal credit market. The planned and dedicated efforts are required from all the dimensions i.e. Government, banks, borrowers etc. At the time of implementation, various models are being followed in the mechanism for the better reach and facilitating the effective analysis. In Malaysia, the model of the group is that five members form the group and eight groups form a center. Each center meets once a week to discuss loan proposal, disburse loans, supervise and monitor problems and to care for the general welfare of the beneficiaries **(Siwar and Talib, 2001)**. Systemic MFI reform necessitates large quality Self help groups with accent on comparatively backward and resource poor regions, suitable training and exposure program, financial assistance to Self help group promoting Institutes (SHPIs), credit rating of Self help groups, financing of Self help groups as a business proposition widening the range of SHPIs by associating larger number of development agencies and greater dissemination of the concept of Self help groups. In the case study from Africa the method for the development of the innovative ways for providing financial assistance in Micro financing. The loan products are specifically designed to benefit the young generations through connecting the education plans with the micro credit programs, eliminating the hazards of the market place. The loans are: Businesses employing young people, Educational, Family-owned businesses. PPIC work projects are being run which provide micro finance and educational training to the youngsters **(Hosseini, Redfern, and Carothers, 2006)**. There are some of the commonly tested strategies in case of micro financing by the successful institutions running around the world. As explained by **Morduch (1999)**, the approaches have their benefits tested on the regular lending. One of the least remarked upon but most unusual features of most microfinance credit contracts is that repayments must start nearly immediately after disbursement. Programs typically begin by lending just small amounts and then increasing loan size upon satisfactory repayment. The repeated nature of the interactions and the credible threat to cut off any future lending when loans are not repaid can be exploited to overcome information problems and improve efficiency, whether lending is group-based or individual-based. While few programs require collateral, many have substitutes. For example, programs following the Grameen model require that borrowers

contribute to an “emergency fund” in the amount of 0.5 percent of every unit borrowed (beyond a given scale). The emergency fund provides insurance in cases of default, death, disability, etc., in amounts proportional to the length of membership. The Bank Rakyat Indonesia’s unit desa program is one of the few programs to require collateral explicitly. BancoSol also stresses the role of solidarity groups in assuring repayments, but twenty eight percent of its portfolio had some kind of guarantee beyond the solidarity group. When the question arises for microfinance programs for meeting their financial promise, the reports have the different perspective.

There is a need for continuing studies to understand the phenomenon of self-sustainability and an increased emphasis on helping MFIs become self-sustaining. Research findings are cited, leading to the conclusion that self-sustaining MFIs are more likely to impact poverty than those dependent on outside subsidies and grants to remain operational (**Husain, 2008**). The factor contributing to the success of BRI (Bank Rakyat Indonesia) are listed out as: keep on adapting the practice with environmental changing, innovativeness in choosing collaterals, well-trained and dedicated staffs operating a simple, transparent system, clear incentives to staffs and clients, tight internal supervision and audit capacities and financial procedures and sound financial risk management etc. which are contributing to its success as well. Smaller account opening balance, insurance cover with saving account, term deposits available for the minimum period of even 7 days, a transferable deposit certificate (**Hartungi R., 2007**). Lastly the donor money should try to reduce the obstacles in order to reach the segment of the population that still not have access to financial services. Private investors should direct money towards equity investments in order to support growth in the industry. **Lard and Barres (2007)** has recommended that the excitement and diversity of the new financial players may inadvertently result in a scramble to invest in micro financing institutions, regardless of their long term financial outlook. While the poor need more integrated programs and the moderate poor need more credit. Public education about the real impact of financial services for the poor people, through advertising campaigns and open debate forums, may cultivate realistic expectations and therefore long term support for microfinance as the part of the overall development of economy. It is necessary to realign the public’s perception to micro finance with the practitioners’ experience. Cell phone services will reduce the transaction cost for both the clients and institutions by reducing the

transportation cost and paper work. The increased transparency will help in funding decisions, segmenting the market, and designing the appropriate products. Public-private partnership should be promoted since it encourages innovations. The future growth of the industry dependent on the private investor willingness to take equity positions in institutions. However, in order for microfinance to continue to serve the poor, the current attitude and expectations have to be realigned with empirical realities. In applying the concept of social capital to these micro credit cases, it becomes clear that the work of MFI managers is not simply a matter of accounting or repayment of loans. Instead, a significant amount of their time and energy needs to go into facilitating the processes of social capital among their bank members (**Woodworth, 2008**). The financial intermediaries worldwide are seeking mechanisms for participating in micro lending. A simple model has been developed where a bank may use informed/local capitalists" as intermediaries for on-lending. But the availability of multiple credit sources provides borrowers with an incentive to default voluntarily, making the bank's on-lending mechanism a non-starter. The variables are listed out as income and savings pattern, political awareness, attitude, networking and sharing, mobility and family planning etc. Conclusively, micro finance can contribute for poverty reduction and strengthening the risk management capacity of the poor. There must be disaster preparedness especially in natural disasters, economic crisis and civil conflicts. It is essential for MFIs to develop a strategy for maintaining liquidity in a disaster situation, especially keeping disaster loan funds (DLFs) in reserve to help affected households. Disaster management is a dynamic process that could ideally be developed during normal times and tested in actual disasters but it requires careful planning and commitment on the part of all stakeholders (**Kumar and Newport, 2007**). Micro Banking Bulletin 1998, a recent survey finds 34 profitable programs among a group of 72 with a "commitment" to financial sustainability. This does not imply, however, that half of all programs worldwide are self-sufficient. The hundreds of programs outside the base 72 continue to depend on the generosity of donors (e.g., Grameen Bank and most of its replicators do not make the list of 72, although BancoSol and BRI do). Some experts estimate that no more than one percent of NGO programs worldwide are currently financially sustainable and perhaps another 5 percent of NGO programs will ever cross the hurdle (**Morduch, 1999**).

Many of the authors like **Mwenda and Muuka (2004)** and **Rena and Tesfy (2007)** has advocated flexibility into operations and careful government regulation ad

supervision of MFIs. Bank employees must be paid as per their work. If the rewards are related with the inputs, the sector can grow. Mechanisms should be created for the exchange of knowledge and experience among regional and sub-regional microfinance practitioners, including the use of the Internet, dissemination of written material, field level practitioner exchanges and best practice workshops. Regional coordinating committees and sub-regional conferences can bring together microfinance policy makers, leaders and representatives from bilateral, multilateral and intergovernmental development partners to access and compare microfinance progress among each region and it also ensures complimentary rather than competing policies (**Rena and Tesfy, 2007**). This requires focused attention on high cost of micro credit operations, limited sources of funds for micro credit, determination of suitable rate of interest for extending micro credit to ensure long term viable operations, networking with the locally feasible integrated development projects and business competence (**Sharma M., 2005**). Financial intermediaries worldwide are seeking mechanisms for participating in micro lending. **Bubna and Chowdhry (2007)** explored whether a coalition of local capitalists, effectively limiting borrower's opportunity for defaulting multiple times, might be sufficient to facilitate on-lending. Instead, it is found that a monopoly moneylender with superior enforcement technology can out-compete the local capitalist coalition if the moneylender also enjoys the smallest transactions costs of lending. It is shown that a credible competitive threat to the monopoly moneylender can only arise if the local capitalist coalition can also be made cost-effective either by direct subsidies or by measures such as standardization, economies of scale and implementation of best practices. It is argued that Franchising is one potential mechanism that could deliver both cost-efficiencies as well as ability for local capitalists to form a coalition.

The strategic donor investments in a handful of well-managed institutions that offer a simple, easily-replicable financial product could lead to large gains in access to finance for poor. However, this approach could sacrifice other objectives of financial sector development, such as product and institutional diversity, which could be promoted after the initial expansion has taken place. Governments can also have a crucial role in promoting access to microfinance by ensuring macro-economic stability, enforcing a simple regulatory structure and developing communications networks that reduce transaction costs. Another lesson is that while visionary leadership cannot simply be franchised, the internal management systems that

led to the scaling- up can be replicated in other settings. These interventions may be particularly appropriate for the poorest households, which face the greatest risks of income fluctuations and have the greatest need for a range of financial and non-financial services. Moreover, while the provision of microcredit can enhance a woman's status in the eyes of other household members, social mobilization and legal education interventions in conjunction with credit are likely to have a more significant effect than credit alone. However this does not imply that microfinance institutions ought to provide these services. In many cases organizations may prefer to specialize in providing microfinance and facilitate linkages to providers of other non-credit interventions. Hence, subsidies can be justified to support 'infant' microfinance institutions as long as there is a viable route to institutional sustainability. Another lesson is that while visionary leadership cannot simply be 'franchised', the systems and formal rules that govern the successful microfinance industry in Bangladesh can to an extent be replicated. These vary according to the size of the organization but by and large, these organizations delegate significant decision-making authority away from head-offices, are able to monitor individual staff performance and have linked staff incentives with program targets. Client feedback and program monitoring are also crucial. As organizations grow, the willingness to change products based on this feedback and to tailor products for niche markets is critical for success (**Zaman, 2004**). At first glance, banks appear well positioned to offer financial services to ever-increasing numbers of microfinance clients and to earn a profit. Banks have several advantages over non-bank, micro lending NGOs. They are regulated institutions fulfilling the conditions of ownership, financial disclosure, and capital adequacy that help ensure prudent management. Many have physical infrastructure, including a large network of branches, from which to expand and reach out to a substantial number of microfinance clients. They have well-established internal controls and administrative and accounting systems to keep track of a large number of transactions. Their ownership structures of private capital tend to encourage sound governance structures, cost-effectiveness, and profitability, all of which lead to sustainability. Because they have their own sources of funds (deposits and equity capital), they do not have to depend on scarce and volatile donor resources as done by NGOs. They offer loans, deposits, and other financial products that are, in principle, attractive to a microfinance clientele. All of these advantages could give banks a special edge over micro lending NGOs in providing microfinance services (**Baydas, Graham, and**

Valenzuela, 1997).

Most academic and policy discussion on micro entrepreneurs in developing countries focuses on their access to credit, and assumes their human capital to be fixed. However, a growing number of microfinance organizations are attempting to build the human capital of micro-entrepreneurs in order to improve the livelihood of their clients and help further their mission of poverty alleviation. Using a randomized control trial, it has been measure the marginal impact of adding business training to a Peruvian village banking program for female micro entrepreneurs. Treatment groups received thirty to sixty minute entrepreneurship training sessions during their normal weekly or monthly banking meeting over a period of one to two years. Control groups remained as they were before, meeting at the same frequency but solely for making loan and savings payments. It is found that the treatment led to improved business knowledge, practices and revenues. The microfinance institution also had direct benefits through higher repayment and client retention rates. Larger effects found for those that expressed less interest in training in a baseline survey have important implications for implementing similar market-based interventions with a goal of recovering costs (**Karlan and Valdivia, 2006**). Micro lending is growing in Eastern Europe, Russia and China as a flexible means of widening access to financial services, both to help alleviate poverty and to encourage private-sector activity. Mechanism has been described that allow these programs to successfully penetrate new segments of credit markets. These features include direct monitoring, regular repayment schedules, and the use of non-refinancing threats. These mechanisms allow the programs to generate high repayment rates from low-income borrowers without requiring collateral and without using group lending contracts that feature joint liability (**Aghion and Morduch, 2003**). It is concluded that the efforts are required for developing the innovative tools to reach the poorest with the least cost. The funds are reallocated to the new and untested institutional base and from traditional poverty alleviation programs to micro financing. **Ledgerwood (1999)** stated that virtually all MFI innovations had come from subsidized MFIs. Two of the significant innovations in the MFI industry are “group-based lending” (joint borrowing and joint liability without collateral) and “village banking” (provision of financial services to the world’s poorest families so they can create their own jobs, raise household incomes, and improve their standard of living). A number of banks and NGOs are organising the awareness campaigns and offering courses for the training of the bank

officials and MFIs, SMME clients, service providers and development of the individual borrower clients. One of the examples is BANKSETA Micro financing Skill Set program initiated in the year 2004 to ensure the skill development and professionalism in the system through the wide coverage of bank employees, MFIs and NGOs all over India.

There are a number of problems and hindrances are present in the growth path of Micro financing to develop the economy as a whole. Like **Knight and Hossain (2008)**, **Morduch (1999)** and **Buckley (1998)** etc., many of the researchers have focused on the issue of problems faced under micro financing. Though the methods to diagnose the pulse of the economy in each nation has varied over the different approaches but the objective were centralized. There are good reasons for excitement about the promise of microfinance, especially given the political context, but there are also good reasons for caution. Alleviating poverty through banking is an old idea with a checkered past. Poverty alleviation through the provision of subsidized credit was a centrepiece of many countries' development strategies from the early 1950s through the 1980s, but these experiences were nearly all disasters. Some of the researchers do mention the political influence on the success of Micro financing due to credit diversion to the politically powerful away from the intended recipients (**Morduch, The microfinance promise, 1999**). Most of the problems associated with MFIs are same as the governance problem, funding of loans and advances, huge unnerved market, lack of functional policy framework, inept management, the policy should be decided at the national level to facilitate the diversified micro finance services on a long term on suitable basis for the poor (**Emeni, 2008**). In Africa various factors worked is historical precedent, absence or weakness of property rights, scarcity and economic survival, particular role expectations, social sanctions and cultural standards and the lure of rural links and real estate (**Buckley, 1998**). Male dominance is considered one of the problems faced by Micro financing (**Morduch, The microfinance promise, 1999**). In India a system the internal learning system (ILS) has been developed as one way of making the assessment. ILS attempts to involve all the participants in a development program from illiterate participants, village groups, field officers to program managers in the process of tracking and learning from the changes and planning for the better outcomes. ILS uses impact assessment analysis and planning activities as a teaching and empowering tool for the poor women so that they can get a better understanding of their development situation; make more strategic decisions regarding their use of micro credit and

livelihood opportunities; and struggle individually and collectively to overcome social problems. At the same time the field staff gets the useful information about participants' lives and livelihoods and is able to adjust their organizing strategies to better assist the participants (**Noponen, 2005**). Various challenges are listed out by **Knight and Hossain (2008)** within Barbados and the Caribbean i.e. High social and economic development, Competition, Poor repayment discipline, Insufficient technical cooperation between business and support organizations, High social and economic development, Poverty targeting, Overemphasis on collateral, Divergent missions, High subsidization presents a major challenge to sustainability, Strong government intervention and High transaction costs. Most of these factors are true for the other developing countries also. **Kasim and Jayasooria (2001)** has explored another perspective. Firstly, it discussed the role of micro- finance institutions (MFIs) in promoting the informal sector in Malaysia; secondly, it identified the issues and policy measures on MFIs and the informal sector. It suggested that there is a strong need for having formal policies and institutions to service the informal sector and tap their potential for economic regeneration. Various bottlenecks discussed are the outreach to the poor, economic crisis, lack of conducive policy environment, policy measures, legal entities, and deregulated interest rates, Government funding priority area, regulations and supervision and saving mobilization. Existing literature indicates that transaction costs are a major contributor to high interest rates on micro credit loans. **Helms and Reille (2004)** and **Fernando (2006)** argue that, interest rate ceilings are not likely to be a solution to these concerns of the policy makers. **Helms and Reille (2004)** discussed that the reasons for high transaction costs in micro credit are numerous – the most important being that the average microfinance loan size is small and hence the transaction cost on a percentage basis for a microfinance loan tends to be higher. The reasons for high transaction costs in micro credit are numerous– the most important being that the average microfinance loan size is small and hence the transaction cost on a percentage basis for a microfinance loan tends to be higher. Further, the group lending model adopted entails peculiar costs such as group formation costs, costs on training the borrowers on the procedures to be followed, a higher degree of supervision and a higher frequency of installment payments (usually weekly or bi-monthly). This is not due to poor return rates, but instead to the inherent nature of microfinance; the transactional costs involved in making many small loans will always be larger than those required to make one big loan. Legal reserve requirements are

higher in some of the countries where the banks are not able to utilise their scarce resources and thus micro lending is discouraged.

The success of micro financing depends upon the health of the institutions responsible for its operations. Several studies confirm that high loan default rate is the primary cause of failure of MFIs. Other studies provide evidence of the positive and negative influences on MFI sustainability. Many studies analyzing the financial sustainability of MFI are based on four key indicators of performance that determine success or failure of MFIs (**Holtmann and Grammling, 2005**). Taking a specific case, it is argued that regulating microfinance operations and activities is likely to strengthen microfinance institutions' (MFIs) financial sustainability. This in turn could provide an important source of finance to small firms. This contribution probably comes at an opportune moment when the Tanzanian government is in the process of formulating a framework to regulate and supervise microfinance institutions (**Satta, 2004**). In another perspective, the diverse potentials are found that the formal and semiformal financial institutions- agricultural banks, microfinance banks, microfinance NGOs, financial cooperatives, and other indigenous financial systems have to reach out to the rural poor of respective nations. Any monolithic view that expects a single type of microfinance institution to dominate the rural financial markets is to be denied. To develop effective rural financial systems, some policy implications are drawn, such as reforms of agricultural banks, adoption of market-based policy framework, development of retail capacities of microfinance institutions, progressive establishment of legal and regulatory framework for microfinance, improvement in governance of indigenous financial systems, and importance of savings mobilization (**Fukui and Llanto, 2006**). The legal barriers are also explored to the sustainability of micro financing institutions (MFI) and it argues that the international development community should promote formal partnerships between commercial banks and MFIs. The increased profitability, stability, and growth potential that these partnerships will bring to MFIs will allow them to expand their scope and continue to foster economic growth in developing communities worldwide. The public private partnerships are required for the improvements and the government should develop the legal framework and the development schemes should be launched (**O'Rourke, 2006**). The picture of various countries is presented in the different perspective by the authors in Kenya. The approach of the Micro financing of specific country should be based upon the level of the people of the respective region. The

Government needs to take into account transaction costs when examining the interest rates charged by microfinance institutions. Regional variations in transaction costs – higher in less developed areas – indicate that a uniform cap on interest rates may in fact drive away MFIs from difficult locations. Since group formation time and consequently group formation cost is lower in areas where awareness about microcredit is high. The MFI industry would benefit if there is a campaign spreading basic awareness about the concepts of group microcredit in remote areas through local print/radio media. The costs of the campaigns could perhaps be borne or shared by the Government (**Shankar, 2007**). Microfinance, while undoubtedly faced by several challenges, is of indisputable relevance to the Barbadian context as demonstrated by its high demand. In enabling livelihoods, it directly improves quality of life and promotes poverty reduction. Microfinance clients thus become more empowered and self-sufficient. The government policy initiatives described above are positive, as they reflect a willingness to achieve real social and economic change within the Barbadian society in Barbados (**Knight and Hossain, 2008**). Most of the entities providing microfinance services are non-formal and semi-formal institutions not subject to prudential regulations which apply to banks and other formal-sector institutions. The research provides a framework for addressing regulatory issues which impact MFI operations and institutional development. Various disadvantages are noted creating a separate set of regulations for specialized treatment, or for universal regulation of MFIs. It is shown that existing regulatory principles can be adapted to address coverage appropriate for MFIs and those activities that may need to be regulated. The research helps in developing guidelines to establish a regulatory environment which permits MFIs to progressively evolve into institutions capable of wider outreach and achieving critical mass in operations. Banking laws in many countries compartmentalize and segment markets and institutions, constraining MFI innovations and making their institutional development difficult. The discussion generated some principal conclusions about regulating the organization and operations of various categories of MFIs. The conclusions arrived at are enumerated as: (i) Require standard registration documents and procedures i.e. no different than those imposed on regular corporate entities including the designation of a central governmental agency for registration as corporate entities; (ii) Establish clearly understood thresholds for fund-mobilization from the general public as well as the non-public wholesale sectors which should require registration, reporting and monitoring, and compliance with registration and licensing

procedures; (iii) Allow minor deposit-taking under an exclusion provision in the banking law, and authorize wholesale deposit-funding linked to registration and minimum capital requirements for certain types of MFIs not licensed as banks; (iv) Allow limited deposit-taking activities from the public under a limitation provision (linked to a risk assets-to-capital or liabilities-to-capital level lower than the limit for regular banks) together with requirements for maintaining liquidity reserves; (v) Establish recommended limits on issuance of wholesale deposit substitute instruments, linked to registration and minimum capitalization requirements; (vi) Establish internal governance and self-regulation structures and processes. Ratios are useful only as complementary tools in the exercise of prudent management by the board and senior management (**Greuning, Gallardo, and Randhawa, Dec, 1998**). Many of the researchers talked about the regulation of the sector. They supported the regulatory framework due to benefits associated with the same. MFIs access to voluntary deposits and other commercial funds sources and MFIs' financial sustainability is directly influenced by the extent of regulations imposed in the system. Despite the above arguments, a consensus seems to emerge on four key issues, that is: (i) Development of regulatory framework should take account of the specific institutional environment. (ii) The regulatory method adopted must promote a competitive balance among all financial institutions to facilitate their growth and financial sustainability. (iii) An excessive level of prudential regulatory requirements should not be imposed on emerging microfinance sectors. (iv) A regulatory structure that is too detailed in its prescription of prudential requirements may stifle, rather than promote, the growth of industry (**Satta, 2004**).

Judging and evaluating the performance and the outreach of the micro financing in the different regions have always remained the area of interest for the researchers and the policy makers for framing the better and suitable policy and judging implementation effectiveness. Two key performance indicators for MFIs are (a) quality of the portfolio, i.e., lower default and arrears rate, and (b) the quantity of the portfolio, i.e., number of borrowers. (**Holtmann and Grammling, 2005**). In Bangladesh, the study shows that there are overlapping programs but still there is a considerable unmet demand. The demand for more and better service products from MFIs is growing day by day because of limitations with prevailing programs and the limited client outreach by Government, Banks, and MFIs altogether (Azad, Shamsuddoha, and Hayder Arif, 2004). The Different levels of poverty require different types

of services. The researchers have been challenging the basic assumptions that the micro financing is the cure for the poverty in the world. The research on micro financing always tried to answer the questions that whether the micro finance reaches the poorest of the poor, investors will invest and reinvest the disbursed funds in the business only and the increased earnings will break the vicious circle of poverty. The impact vary from positive to negative depending upon the region covered, population under study, terms and conditions of the scheme, time period for implementation and the support by the respective Government Publicly-funded job training program in USA had changed the lives of the poor households. This was ineffective for Africa-American children. Most of these programs have their shorter span due to the fact that they are expensive and seldom justify their cost. Many of the researchers are positive for impact of Micro financing on poverty elimination and human growth. Positive impact is shown in Bangladesh on income, production and employment particularly in the rural non-farm sector (**Khandker, Samad, and Khan, 1998**). Another attempt examines the financial services and devices used by dwellers of Kalibasti, a squatter settlement in West Delhi. It highlights the embeddedness of financial devices used by residents in wider kinds of relationships with relatives, co-residents, employers, 'patrons' and others. It is concluded that access to adequate services does not necessarily correspond with access to formal or semi-formal services as is often presented by micro-finance advocates. Rather it reflects people's awareness, job and income security, and capacity to leverage personal networks, all of which contribute to the capability of squatter residents to make financial relations and services work for them. The banks are treated as the source for making the deposits for ensuring safety. Bank accounts are not generally used as the income-smoothing device. The people generally prefer the smaller savings at their homes rather than making the deposits in the banks. There are complaints of being cheated also by the deposit collectors on the basis of confusing terms and conditions also. Various factors are studied to judge the availability and availing of the banking facilities by the poor people in the place (**Ruthven, 2002**). In another research, it concluded that microfinance has strong capacity to drive economic growth and poverty reduction in Eritrea (**Rena and Tesfy, 2007**). There is a lot of literature available to evaluate the effects of micro-credit projects on the poor. Most of them concluded on the positive aspect of micro financing but there is lack of hundred percent favoritism. The data collected in Sichuan Province in 1999 is utilised to investigate whether

micro-credit projects have targeted the poor and whether participation in the micro-credit project increases the likelihood of migration and switching to off-farm jobs. The conclusion is drawn that although the micro-credit programs did not help in increasing the assets of the participants, it did help to move one or more of their members into an off-farm job. The findings indicate that there is a great deal of benefit in supporting micro-credit programs (**Li, Rozelle, and Zhang, 2004**). The hope is that much poverty can be alleviated and that economic and social structures can be transformed fundamentally by providing financial services to low-income households. These institutions, united under the banner of microfinance, share a commitment of serving clients that have been excluded from the formal banking sector. Globally, there are now about 8 to 10 million households served by microfinance programs and some practitioners are pushing to expand to 100 million poor households by 2005. Advocates who lean left highlight the “bottom-up” aspects, attention to community, focus on women, and most importantly, the aim to help the underserved. Those who lean right highlight the prospect of alleviating poverty while providing incentives to work, the nongovernmental leadership, the use of mechanisms disciplined by market forces, and the general suspicion of ongoing subsidisation (**Morduch, 1999**). As an effective financial tool for socio-economic development, today microfinance has gained enormous success in tackling poverty on a global scale and helping various governmental and non-governmental actors to achieve their Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). Given the positive impact of microfinance on small business, agriculture, education, health, and other indicators of development, the practice of micro-credit is crucial to poverty alleviation, which is a key feature of many Caribbean government agendas. The practice was made to shed the light on how the governments in the Caribbean region have incorporated microfinance in their economic development efforts. Drawing on contemporary practices, we examine the challenges faced by the microfinance sector within the Caribbean, with an emphasis on the Barbadian context (**Knight and Hossain, 2008**). As an effective financial tool for socio-economic development, today microfinance has gained enormous success in tackling poverty on a global scale and helping various governmental and non-governmental actors to achieve their Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). Cross-country experience clearly shows that micro credit is the key to socio-economic transformation. **Hosseini, Redfern, and Carothers (2006)** demonstrate that micro credit does not only deliver micro benefits but has also brought about a

silent revolution in rural areas. A significant instrument of promotion of micro credit in India in a sustainable manner has been the Self help group program and its linkage with banks. The government supported micro-credit program under joint liability in Swarna-Jayanti Gram Swarozgari Yojana Scheme in India is able to reach to the ultra poor and vulnerable section of the rural population of West Bengal where most of the participants are rural married women. The scheme is helping them to reduce their acuteness of poverty but still fails to reduce their vulnerability. It is also helping the participants to improve their empowerment. The group leaders do not take any undue advantage from their respective groups to improve their economic conditions more quickly than other fellow ordinary members (**Kundu, 2008**). The research provides evidence, in the form of case studies, demonstrating that with a relatively low investment of resources, women are empowered to contribute to the growth of the small business sector which is a cornerstone of a robust private sector. Mennonite Economic Development Associates (MEDA) has had varying degrees of success and preliminary findings suggest that value chain projects derive greater benefit from targeted activities than do microfinance programs. The impact of business women's efforts extends well beyond their own businesses, to finance family enterprises, educate children, improve household nutrition, organize community groups, and build more equitable social structures (**Jones, Snelgrove, and Muckosy, 2006**).

As far as the past is concerned micro financing was not able to meet the greatest promises claimed by its recommenders as well as practitioners. Many researchers like **Morduch (1999)**, **Holvoet (2004)** and **Pitt and Khandker (1998)** are unable to find out the positive translators in micro financing as claimed. The reports suggested that Micro financing has not been successful till date in different countries wherever practiced. Most of the program ended up with grants, subsidies and soft terms of loans from the donors. Even the financially sound programs are not able to benefit the poor deserving population. Even as per Micro Banking Bulletin (1998), a recent survey shows that even poverty-focused programs with a “commitment” for achieving financial sustainability cover only about 70 percent of their full costs (**Morduch, 1999**). Since its inception to till date, there has been tremendous growth of organizations, known as MFIs (Micro Finance Institutions), in this field to deal with the micro finance/credit activities. Despite this, the poverty situation of the poor people who have already used the micro finance programs was not improved substantially. A variety of variables (rank

wise) are considered to measure the impact of microfinancing on poverty alleviation—Profit/Business Expansion, Consumption/Calorie Intake, Housing/Shelter, Income/Resource/Saving, Expenditure on Education, Better Clothing, Social Awareness, Loan Repayment Ability and Household Durables. Study reveals that even though the average net worth of the loanees has increased the percentage increase in average net worth after use of micro finance was only 12.73%. The net worth of 28% loanees has been decreased after use of micro finance. The study indicates that most of the loanees (98%) reported that they wanted to leave the program because they got only one type of loan from the MFI (**Azad, Shamsuddoha, and Hayder Arif, 2004**). The extent of the impact of every program varies due to number of factors such as governance, framework, and sources of finance, demographic features of the beneficiaries as well as the region covered and many other unrecognizable factors. An attempt estimated the impact of participation, by gender, in the Grameen Bank and two other group-based micro credit programs in Bangladesh on labor supply, schooling, household expenditure, and assets. The empirical method uses a quasi-experimental survey design to correct for the bias from unobserved individual and village-level heterogeneity. It is found that program credit has a larger effect on the behavior of poor households in Bangladesh when women are the program participants. For example, annual household consumption expenditure increases 18 taka for every hundred additional taka borrowed by women from these credit programs, compared with 11 taka for men (**Pitt and Khandker, 1998**). Using data from a South India household survey, the research examines how microfinance impacts schooling and literacy, how credit interests the household, and who brings it in. Regression results show that, in the case of direct bank-borrower credit delivery, it does not matter whether credit enters the household through the mother or the father. However, large differences occur when mothers obtain credit through women's groups. Analysis indicates that combined financial and social-group intermediation leads to higher educational inputs and outputs, mainly for girls. The funds are easily assessable through the social-groups network (**Holvoet, 2004**). As noted above, microfinance programs have yet to receive that kind of scrutiny. Visits to areas served by microfinance programs show what cannot be seen in books of accounts—earnings from microfinance participation are funding new houses, further education for children, new savings accounts, and new businesses. But are these changes more remarkable than those occurring elsewhere? (**Morduch, 1999**). However, microfinance is not a universal

remedy for poverty and related development challenges, but rather an important tool in the mission of poverty eradication. As microfinance becomes more widely accepted and moves into the mainstream, the supply of services to the poor may likewise increase, improving efficiency and outreach, while lowering costs. This, in turn, can have a multiplier effect on people's standard of living. Perhaps the greatest contribution of microfinance is that it empowers people, providing them with confidence, self-esteem, and the financial means to play a larger role in the development process. The potential of microfinance far exceeds the micro-level, scaling-up to address macro-problems associated with poverty eradication. The rationale of this approach was that the direct provision of such goods and services is likely to relieve absolute poverty more immediately than alternative strategies, since growth strategies usually fail to benefit the intended target and the productivity and income of the poor depend in the first place on the direct provision of health and education facilities **(Rena and Tesfy, 2007)**. The Savings and Micro Credit Program (SMCP), an organisation under the umbrella of the Ministry of National Development, provides major microfinance to women entrepreneurs. A small group of men and women were interviewed to ascertain their successes and problems with microcredit and enterprise development. It discovers how the women benefited from the microfinance program and got rid of their poverty. While female credit had a very significant positive effect on the likelihood that a woman had independent savings, it did not have an effect on the likelihood that a woman had savings that she herself could control **(Pitt, Khandker, and Cartwright, 2003)**.

The micro financing may not necessarily result into micro units, creation of jobs, and development of the region due to the fluctuating income pattern of the poor families which even find difficult to make the monthly contribution for the deposits. Most of the studies fail to establish a clear relation between the micro finance and the poverty. Micro financing can't be directly considered as the eradicator of poverty due to lack of sufficient data. Microfinance can reduce the vulnerability of the poor but it is not a poverty cure-all **(Lard and Barres, 2007)**. Amount of per capita periodic thrift has a positive relation with members' perception reflected in their educational status. Unity in purpose of loans and intention, and the practice of rotation of lending, backed by relatively higher economic status among the concerned group members reflect higher lending. Moderate and less number of loans associate with lack of unity in purpose, and lack of intention to rotate the lending. Unlike the low lending

groups, which were hesitant to lend for non-food consumption purpose, moderate lending groups seem to have diversified their lending purposes. Economic statuses of the group members tend to reflect the differential number of loans across the survey locations. There is no conclusive evidence on the bias due to caste heterogeneity. Unlike the expectation, revolving fund or bank loan assistance did not result in the adverse effects on the group cohesion. Contrary to this, groups exhibited reason in the choice of funds across the purposes. The broader perception is that own funds are meant for saving and external funds for investment (**Nagendra Kumar, 2006**).

Micro financing is extending its perspective to the varying dimensions such as insurance in the different sectors, entrepreneurial development projects, offering the necessities at the concessional rates etc. which is facilitating the overall growth of rural India through the effective targeting of the borrowed funds under different models of micro financing. In addition to providing loans, some of the programs also offer education on health issues, gender roles, and legal rights (**Morduch, The microfinance promise, 1999**). A new concept HMF (Housing Micro financing) is emerging these days. Several countries reached at the appreciable level of micro credit to the poor household is now promoting the finance or the construction and the repairs of the house in the village territory in India. A study conducted in Vietnam on the basis of the qualitative and quantitative data is positive for the future prospects of the same in the developing countries like it (**Cornelis and ruben, 2008**). The research is being conducted on the micro financing from the housing loans perspective. The loans specifically provided for the house constructions and renovations are also the options being availed by the companies. Best practice in housing microfinance involves loans at unsubsidized interest rates and short terms, relative to traditional mortgage finance. A key to success of the effort at mainstreaming microfinance lies in joining the institutions and expertise of the microenterprise finance community with that of the housing and housing finance community (**Ferguson and Haider, 2000**). The research in the area is the practical guide for the implementation of the micro housing finance in the sector to improve the housing standards for the poor. The real estate sector is encouraged in the rural areas by providing the baseline for the existing companies to judge their capacity to enter the sector. It guided with practical guidance to MFIs adopting the housing program in addition to the existing line of micro-finance services and inputs about any market study, profiling the customers, product design, pricing of the product,

affordability of the clients, income assessment, loan assessment, operational procedures, risk coping mechanisms and technical backup guidance. MFIs should also ensure that housing micro-finance suits their strategy from institutional and financial perspectives (**Kumar, Sanu, and Newport, 2008**). After the Russia's 1998 financial crisis Kyrgyzstan's economy needs a revival. The discussion, at present, focuses on the new areas and the role that market rate housing finance can play in improving living conditions in them. It is the overview of the market to judge the chances for the progress of housing finance in the region for the small and micro enterprises (**Struyk and Roy, 2006**). There is the new stream for facilitating the micro level i.e. by way of micro insurance. Micro insurance provides the safeguard to the rural population for the disastrous conditions e.g. famines, earthquakes, tsunami etc. There are various models present in micro insurance sector i.e. Partner-agent model, direct sales model, mutuality credit, community- based model. But there are various challenges to be met before adopting any model for the success. The conditions suggested for the success of micro financing are simple insurance instruments, low transaction cost, affordability, location, financial literacy and role of govt (**Fukui and Llanto, 2006**). The score for general readiness of MFIs in Iran revealed a remarkable figure. Accordingly, it is suggested that these institutes should enter this business field incrementally and invest in this particular domain (**Torkestani and Ahadi, 2008**). The process of global health sector development has been witnessing a trend of surfacing of new financing options for health care. The poverty-ill-health nexus has become a vicious circle due to chronic income poverty, dropping down of government spending to public health sector, escalation of health care costs, emerging trend of global illnesses and the dominance of private sector in health care service delivery. In this context, the most suitable option to enhance affordability and access to health care is widening the available means as well as find out new options for financing health care. Nevertheless, the process is not automatic as groups, like individuals, may not consider health care as a priority unless the necessity comes. However to ensure more viability and sustainability of the mechanism, an inter-sectoral coordination with the government for support and forming a welfare fund at the Self help group level to meet the requirements of ambulatory health care services are suggestible (**Gopalan, 2007**). The newer concept of using the community based Organizations for the implementation of the health care programs in the region of Kenya by facilitating the poor for meeting their health care expenses. The records or the data is very encouraging as per

the implementation records show (**Molyneux, Hutchison, Chuma, and Gilson, 2007**). The current discussions are now emerging with the concept of urban microfinancing. The system has its roots to the parts of the country where there is existence of numerous MFIs and for growth they need to explore new areas and the rural dimensions are financially satisfied.

There are worldwide examples in the micro financing i.e. The Grameen Bank in Bangladesh; BancoSol in Bolivia; Rakyat in Indonesia; Credit Desa in Indonesia and Village Bank in Latin America. Though the approaches followed by different institutions may vary in terms of the approach towards profit, welfare to society, terms and conditions for lending and coverage group but the primary advantage to the society is the availability of easy credit to the financially disadvantaged group. The programs also use dynamic incentives, regular repayment schedules, and collateral substitutes to help maintain high repayment rates (**Morduch, 1999**). The use of financial services as a development tool has taken a variety of forms over the past twenty five years - rural credit schemes offering heavily subsidised loans to poor farmers, microfinance organisations providing working capital loans to predominately female micro-entrepreneurs, and a variety of organisations offering a range of financial services (credit, savings and insurance) to help poor households increase incomes and reduce their vulnerability to income fluctuations. Microfinance providers in Asia and Latin America have been world leaders, and the demonstration effect of their successes has helped to build substantial microfinance industries in countries such as Indonesia, Bangladesh and Bolivia. Africa has fewer well-known programs but some notable performers and growing microfinance sectors nonetheless; while regions such as the South Pacific have few if any microfinance successes. **Donaghue (2004)** highlighted some key themes in the development of microfinance, with particular reference to the Asia Pacific region.

The present scenario in India at the various stages of micro financing is quite different from the perspective shown in the theories. **Muhammad Yunus (2004)** writes that “women have greater long-term vision and are ready to bring changes in their life step by step. They are also excellent managers of scarce resources, stretching the use of every resource to the maximum”. The economic argument for microfinance’s focus on female-owned businesses is that female owners are likely to be poorer and more credit constrained, and to use resources more efficiently. The expectations are that there will be higher returns to capital in female-owned firms, but one of the researches provides evidence against the view, finding mean

returns to capital to be zero among female-owned micro-enterprises in Sri Lanka. In contrast, returns to capital for male-owned enterprises are in excess of 11 percent per month. These large returns show that, on average, male-owned enterprises are more likely to generate the return on investment necessary to repay micro-loans. But the results do show that there is a subset of women who have high enough returns to cover the costs of loans, namely poor, high ability women. In case of grants offered in Sri Lank, males have earned higher rates of return than women population. The reason is that they did not invest the grant in their enterprise, or because they did not earn additional profits when the grant was invested (**Mel, McKenzie, and Woodruff, 2008**). The ability of most microfinance institutions (MFIs) to leverage capital and mobilize external resources is generally limited. To support outreach to low-income clients, donated resources are generally leveraged and augmented by borrowing from formal financial institutions or large institutional and individual investors, or accepting limited deposits from the public. It provided a framework for addressing regulatory issues which impact MFI operations and institutional development (**Greuning, Gallardo, and Randhawa, Dec, 1998**). Out of BRAC's total \$160 million expenditure on development programs in 2002, more than 80 percent was financed from its own resources, through the interest income on microcredit as well as surplus from its commercial enterprises (**Zaman, 2004**). There is new trend being followed by the villagers is multiple borrowings. In those parts of India, where the concept of microfinancing on its peak, the poors enjoys multiple MFI memberships at the household levels. They borrow from the different MFIs with the similar geographical coverage at the similar terms and conditions (**Kamath and Srinivasan, 2009**). There is a unique group lending mechanism used by a typical micro finance lender in Haryana, India. The mechanism had three interesting features. Firstly, the groups were initially formed as Rotating, Saving and Credit Associations. This enabled the lender to screen the groups. Second, there was significant heterogeneity within the group in terms of income and educational achievements. Third, the relatively wealthy individuals dominated the decision making process in the group and were able to obtain a disproportionate amount of credit allocated to the group (**Aniket, 2005**).

Thus, Micro financing is the key to growth and prosperity of any economy especially the economically weaker societies with the unequal income distribution pattern. But the development of an innovative mechanism is not sufficient; it must be supported by the effective implementation as per the regional specifications. They need to develop the financial

attitude among the people who have no access to the formal banking system. The growth of micro financing depends upon the efforts put in and dedication shown by the social workers, bank employees, members of the Self help groups or any other party directly or indirectly sharing the burden of implementation of the schemes and have developed the deep roots into the villages and far flung areas which do not enjoy the existence on the maps of official banks coverage. An extensive research is required for the development of the system. Such a research should deal not specifically with the matter on the papers but also need to explore the ground realities for the effective results on the papers. Various researchers fail to start or finish with the target objective due to financial constraints which need attention of the administrators to wide open the funds for the research of the noble cause of the humanity.

Need for the Study

Micro financing has been the least researched area in India. Moreover most of the literature is available on all India perspective. Very few research studies are available analyzing the models adopted, effectiveness of the schemes initiated by the government, survey of the Self help groups operating in rural India, administrative problems faced at the route level etc. Wherever the exploratory studies are available, that too concentrated on national penetration of the mechanism, its related problems and solutions. The exposure of micro financing has not been explored state-wise to see the variation in the coverage area, effectiveness of the policies framed at the state level, promotional tools employed by the commercial banks as well as NGOs in the region and regional problems faced by the group members. In the true spirit, micro financing has been adopted negligibly in various states including Punjab. It is passing through the phase of development with the existence of complete Government machinery as well as socially-recognised and dedicated NGOs in the region which have the major contribution in developing the conceptual clarity among the socially and financially ignorant class of the society. Still various problems act as the hindrance in the path of growth. The research concentrating on the regional problems and the solutions varying with the change in culture, education level and the economic soundness of the people is required. The current study is the step in the direction.

CHAPTER-III

RESEARCH DESIGN

RESEARCH DESIGN

Scope of the study

The study is concentrated in the Jalandhar District. The villages under Municipal Corporation, Jalandhar (MCJ) constitute the universe for the study. The city is divided into ten blocks covered under Deputy Commissioner Office, Jalandhar named as Jalandhar East, Jalandhar West, Adampur, Bhogpur, Shahkot, Lohian, Phillaur, Nurmahal, Rurkan Kalan and Nakodar as per the list obtained from DC (Deputy Commissioner) Office. But as per the list of CDPO office, eleventh block has also been added as Jalandhar Urban. The groups are divided into two categories such as Below Poverty Line (BPL groups) and Above Poverty Line (Non-BPL Groups). A group with the majority of the membership (at least 70%) living below the poverty line is known as BPL group. The poverty status is decided as per the list issued under BPL Census 2002 by Indian Govt.

Objectives

1. To study the level of penetration of micro financing in Jalandhar District.
2. To study the structure and functioning of the Self help groups in Jalandhar District.
3. To study the pattern of usage of finance by SHGs (Self Help Groups).
4. To study the problems faced by SHGs in their operations and suggesting the possible solutions.

Research Design

The study is based on primary data collected through the interview method. Around twenty one cases of Self help groups have been studied to understand and explore the issues under consideration. In-depth interviews of the members of the selected groups in Jalandhar district were conducted in order to analyse the problems associated with the mechanism. The views are collected from the bank officials, Government executives, angan-wadi workers, members of NGOs as well as staff under BDO, CDPO and DC office. The researcher attended the monthly

meeting of Gram Sewikas at ADC Office and examined the gram sewikas posted in the different blocks in the city. The views expressed are collected and compiled in the report. In the interviews, most of questions were open-ended and asked for the opinions, feelings, experience and problems related to micro financing. Each interview has taken more than an hour to interact with the members of the group. All the efforts were taken to use the most local and familiar language and terminology to ensure the complete understanding and comfort in responding. Though this method of data collection is subject to the basic limitation that every respondent may not feel comfortable being open and interactive with the stranger interviewing them but being most suitable method for the more effective and unbiased response, it was selected.

Sample

The geographical region covered for the study is Jalandhar District. As per the official records there are 387 groups in BPL category and 1325 in Non-BPL category. A sample of twenty one groups has been selected from the universe on the basis of convenience sampling approach due to the wide coverage of the district, difficult traceability of the small villages and the lack of telephonic connectability with the Self help groups located at the far-flung areas. Out of these twenty one groups, there are 5 BPL and 16 Non-BPL groups. In addition, the study involves the analysis of the data obtained from the different banks and MFIs dealing with the groups, lead banker in Jalandhar, ADC Office, CDPO, DRDA office. The data with the progress of Self help groups in the region has also been collected from the records of NGOs.

Limitations of the Study

Due to various constraints, the research has been limited to the extent of reviewing the performance of 21 Self help groups within the Jalandhar region. The coverage has been restricted mainly due to the shortage of time. The records with regard to the functioning of Self help groups are available with the BDO Office and CDPO Office. Both the records have been used for the analysis. The year wise records could be made available from the BDO Office only. The research objectives could not be enlarged due to the failure on the part of the private commercial banks to provide the database regarding different Self help groups serviced by them (in order to maintain secrecy). At the level of data collection, the members of Self help groups may not have provided the true information due to fear of the adverse financial affect on them, though the

adequate precaution was taken to convince the respondents regarding confidentiality and the academic use of the inputs provided. In spite of these limitations, the study has been able to shed some worthwhile light on the issues related to SHGs and Micro Finance in Jalandhar district.

CHAPTER IV

**CASE STUDIES OF SHGs IN
JALANDHAR DISTRICT**

CASE STUDIES OF SHGs IN JALANDHAR DISTRICT

CASE –I: *Bibi Jamna Devi Ji SHG*⁷

Location	Vill.Tajpur, PO Lambra, Nakodar Road, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	June 26, 2006
Date of Monthly meeting	5 th of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs. 100/- per month per member
Office Bearers	President: Pyari Secretary: Mahinder Kaur Cashier: Krishna Devi
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly From Non-members - 4% monthly
Total Deposits till Date	Rs. 57,169 (till March, 2009)
Bank Associated	PNB, Lambra, Jalandhar-144026
Details of the Bank Loan	Amount of the loan: Rs. 50,000 Installments: Rs 4,500 per month Remarks: All the installments of loan are paid in time without any delay or default.
Counseling	The group is getting the counseling and some financial assistance from an NGO named as Sports Goods Federation Of India (SGFI), which is primarily acting for anti child labour in sports goods industry.

It is three years old tightly-built group with fourteen members. At this stage they are well managed as SHG. All the members of the group are Females. They are collecting deposits on monthly basis and providing loans to their members and outsiders also. But the rate of interest

⁷ Based on personal interview with the group members, held on 13th July, 2009 at Tajpur, Nakodar Road, Jalandhar.

charged is higher in case of non-members. Providing loans to the outsiders is not permissible under the guidelines for SHGs, but the researcher found only one such group which allow to grant loans to the non-members at double the interest rate than the usual. The internal loan is provided immediately at the demand of the members on the signatures of the office bearers only. The loan seeker is not required to wait for the approval of all the members. These emergent loans are stated in the next monthly meeting of the group. The meetings are monthly held at the decided place. The details of the collected sum, disbursement of the loans till date and the total balance of deposits available with the group are declared in the presence of all the members in the meeting. All the monthly deposits are taken to the bank immediately after the meeting. The members are required to pay Rs10 after 2-3 months to the office bearers for meeting the expenses of traveling and the other petty expenses for the maintenance of the group and management of finance. The loans are generally provided for the period less than six months. The members are also provided with the repeat loans on the timely payments of their previous ones. The range of the loans is Rs.2,000-15,000. The loans are generally paid in time; rather few of them were paid before time. The operations of the group are disturbed by the delay payments of the deposits and repayment of the loan by one or two members. The defaults are strictly dealt with by warning the defaulting member in the monthly meeting in the presence of all the members.

The loan was granted by the Bank on 30th April, 2007 of Rs 50,000 which was returned by EMI in time. The amount of the loan was equally distributed among all the members of the group and was utilized for the purchase of wheat stock for the whole year. As per the response of the members, the amount of the loan has relieved them of the worries of the meals for the entire year. As per the views expressed by the NGO member, with whose efforts the group started, the group members were not at all interested to involve into such time consuming and painful activities. They regarded it as the most unnecessary activity but today they praised the system for being supportive for the poor villagers who do not have the direct access of the banks and the financial services provided by them.

CASE-II: *Guru Kirpa SHG*⁸

Location	Vill.Tajpur, PO Lambra, Nakodar Road, District Jalandhar
Formation Date	October 22, 2007.
Date of Monthly meeting	6 th of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100 per month
Office Bearers	President: Parmjeet Kaur Secretary: Mukesh Rani Cashier: Parmjeet
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly From Non-members - 4% monthly
Total Deposits till Date	Rs. 32,180 (till March, 2009)
Bank Associated	PNB, Lambra, Jalandhar-144026
Bank Loan Details	No Bank Loan has yet been availed by the group.

Well cooperated SHG, with fifteen female members, is eighteen months old. At this stage also some improvements are desired at the group level. They are collecting deposits on monthly basis and providing loans to their members and outsiders also. Availing of the loans is an easy task due to absence of administrative hassles. The needs of all the members are filled in time. The monthly meetings are held at 6th of the every month at the decided location, generally the residence of one of the office bearers. The deposits are generally collected in the meetings. The details of the collected sum, disbursement of the loans till date and the total balance of deposits available with the group are declared in the presence of all the members in the meeting. The fresh monthly deposits are subject to deposit in the bank account immediately. The work does not seem to be very methodical. It was concluded because the loan disbursed two days before the meeting was not even recorded in the register at all and no signature has been taken from the borrower till date. All the payments of the loans are not signed with a revenue stamp. The

⁸ Based on personal interview with the group members, held on 13th July, 2009 at Tajpur, Nakodar Road, Jalandhar.

interest payments are also not periodically deducted from the principle amount as and when they are being received. The president of the group has memorized all the payments and verbally quoted them. But registers does not reflect any such inflow and outflow of cash. The loans to all the members are generally provided for the period less than three months. Till date no loan has been paid back in time. In fact one of the loans of Rs 1000 is provided for one month is now eight months old and nothing has been paid as such. When these defaulters are asked to repay the same, the office bearers face very embarrassing situations and some abusive language also. The main cause is that the aged members of the group do not act as responsible members. The young office bearers responded that these aged defaulters literally catch them from head when they are asked for repayments and threaten to complain against them in front of their family members. The group has not taken any loan and not even planning in the near future. They opined that they are facing a lot of difficulty in recovering their internal lending, hence can't shoulder the burden of responsibility repayment of the joint bank loan.

CASE III: *Sri Guru Ravi Das SHG*⁹

Location	Vill. Manak Rai, PO Manak Rai, Bhogpur, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	June 22, 2004
Category	BPL Category (SC Group)
Date of Monthly meeting	5 th of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Office Bearers	President: Nachatar Kaur Secretary: Parmjeet Kaur Cashier: Nirmala
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Total Deposits till Date	Rs. 63,691 (till Nov, 2008)
Bank Associated	UCO Bank, Bhogpur, District Jalandhar

⁹ Based on personal interview with the group members and gram sevika of the village, held on 30th July, 2009 at Bhogpur, Jalandhar.

Details of the Bank Loan	First Loan: Rs 40,000 from PNB. Second Loan: Rs. 4,40,000 from UCO Bank
Counseling	The group is getting the counseling from the staff members of the respective Bank.

With the member strength of fifteen, the group is well operated. The general matters are discussed among the group members with regard to funds maintained, loans granted and the future course of action for the group. For the disbursement of the loans, the cash is paid to the borrower by obtaining the signature on the register maintained for the purpose. The internal loans are repaid in time rather before time in few cases. The bank loan was also returned within the time frame i.e. one and half year. The loan was taken by PNB Bank on 5th July, 2005 of Rs 40,000, all the EMI were completed on 23rd Nov, 2006. The loan was spent for the building up the water sources in the houses, for purchasing cattle to sell the milk and the construction of the house etc. Rs 4,40,000 loan was taken from UCO Bank which was equally distributed among all the members of the group. Almost all of them have utilized the same for the purchase of cattle for the milk with few exceptions, who have not yet utilized the loan amount till the date of interview. Their lives have become easier with the loan because they are not only earning by selling the milk but also available with the ample of it for their personal use. They were satisfied because the cost of the single cattle of Rs. 30,000-35,000 is not at all affordable for them, but they can definitely pay back the borrowed sum in small monthly installments. The group members were found satisfied by the counseling provided by the staff members of the UCO Bank. At times they do not seem to be satisfied by the treatment provided by PNB bank officials.

CASE IV: *Meena SHG*¹⁰

Location	Vill. Landhra, Bhogpur, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	1 st Aug, 2008
Category	Non- BPL (General Category)
Date of Monthly meeting	9 th of every month at 11:00 am

¹⁰ Based on the meeting with the group members on 30th July, 2009 at UCO Bank Branch, Bhogpur.

Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Office Bearers	<p>President: Sukhwinder Kaur</p> <p>Secretary: Bajan Kaur</p> <p>Cashier: Nirmal Kaur</p>
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Total Deposits till Date	Rs. 7,130 (till March, 2009)
Bank Associated	The group was associated with Canara Bank at its incorporation. Now it is with UCO Bank, Bhogpur, District Jalandhar
Details of the Bank Loan	<p>First Loan: Rs 40,000 from Canara Bank</p> <p>Second Loan: Rs. 4,40,000 from UCO Bank</p>
Counseling	The group is getting the Counseling from the staff members of the respective Bank.

The monthly meetings are held at the Anganwadi Center, Landhra. The deposits are either collected in the meeting or is sometimes paid before the due date. The details of the collected sum, disbursement of the loans till date and the total balance of deposits are presented in the meeting. As far as the meetings are concerned, they are well managed in the presence of Nirmala, the cashier of Meena SHG, who is well aware of all the procedures and can guide the group very well. For the disbursement of the loans, the cash is paid to the borrower after the signature on the register maintained for the purpose. A fixed pattern is followed for internal lending with Rs. 5,000 to the members of the group only. The loans are provided for the period ranging from six months to one year. This group also has the trend of repayment before the due time. The amount of the both the loans were equally distributed among all the members of the group. The borrowed funds are utilized by the group members in the small ancillary activities like purchasing of cattle etc. many of them channelized the funds for the personal consumption. The group members were found satisfied by the counseling provided by the staff members of the UCO Bank. The group faced no administrative obstacles while the grant and disbursement of their loan. The group members belong to the poor class but they are not covered under the BPL List which reflects the political biasness in the welfare issues. This is the real scenario in the

villages, witnessed also by the researcher, that the sarpanches of the village, NRI families and the families possessing cars at their homes are the part of BPL list instead of the people who can't ensure the elementary education to their children. The group members are among the needy population of the rural India which really deserves to be helped and subsidized by the government.

CASE V: *Arsh SHG*¹¹

Location	Vill. Landhra, Bhogpur, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	November 02, 2007.
Category	Non- BPL (General)
Date of Monthly meeting	2 nd of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Office Bearers	President: Manjeet Kaur Secretary: Mamta Rani Cashier: Sanjokta
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Total Deposits till Date	Rs. 31,274 (till Nov, 2008)
Bank Associated	UCO Bank, Bhogpur, District Jalandhar
Details of the Bank Loan	Rs. 1,00,000 from UCO Bank
Counseling	The group is getting the counseling from the staff members of the UCO Bank.

The group has the life of two years with the number of fifteen female members. The loans are provided only to the members on the basis of the deposits made in the group till date. The group members did not appear to be very active but the group was properly managed

¹¹ Based on the remarks given by the group members in the meeting as on 3rd August, 2009 at UCO bank branch Bhogpur.

through the CDPO worker in their village. She not only guides them but also assists their activities. The loans are authenticated by signatures of the borrowers on the registers specifically maintained for the purpose. The amount of loan is in the range of Rs. 1,000 to 5,000. The internal lending is not time bound though the maximum time allowed is ten months but the loans are generally paid in time or before the due date. Normally there is no fixed amount of the installment and pattern followed in the repayment. The loan was proposed to be utilized for the personal needs of the borrowers. The group members were found satisfied by the counseling provided by the staff members of the UCO Bank. The group was the second in the village which seems to have been promoted after the success of the existing group. The office bearers, even after two years of the incorporation of the group, are not well aware of the procedural details with regard to the register maintaining, lending and conducting meetings. The angan wadi worker was the great guide in addition to the already operating in the village.

CASE VI: *Baba Inder Das SHG*¹²

Location	Vill. Manakrai, Bhogpur, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	August 21, 2001
Category	Non- BPL BC (Backward Caste)
Date of Monthly meeting	2 nd of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Office Bearers	President: Kulwinder Kaur Secretary: Kamaljeet Kaur Cashier: Kulwinder Kaur
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Total Deposits till Date	Rs. 1, 37,500 (till Nov, 2008)
Bank Associated	UCO Bank, Bhogpur, District Jalandhar
Details of the Bank Loan	First Loan: Rs 25,000 from PNB

¹² Based upon the interview with the group members at Bhogpur as on 3rd August, 2009.

Second Loan: Rs. 1,00,000 from PNB

Third Loan: Rs.4,40,000 from UCO Bank

Counseling

The group is getting the counseling from the staff members of the UCO Bank.

Out of the total groups surveyed, it is the oldest one with the successful experience of the running a group for more than eight years. The member strength is eleven female members. Not even the office bearers but all the members of the group are well aware of the procedures, guidelines, the subsidies and grants provided by the government for micro financing. The president and the secretary of the group have remarked positively for the system. The payments of deposits and repayment of the loans are very regular within the group. They were proposed to utilize the borrowed money from the bank for purchasing cattle for milking. The group is availing the third loan which is the great achievement because the bank borrowings are not the first preference of the groups in Punjab which could be due to various reasons. The group could be considered as the model for the other SHGs in Punjab. But it lack on the point of investment of the borrowed funds. The huge amount borrowed by the group is divided into smaller parts leaving the fraction not worthwhile for the sound business preposal. If the entire money is channelised into the joint venture with the profit motive, the members can experience a sharp rise in their income. At present also the group has huge accumulated deposits of its own over the years that should be directed towards the sound investment option like manufacturing woolen clothes, gud, sahkkar, stitched garments and detergents etc. All the products need a specialized technique only, the training for which is being provided by the different training sessions organized by the governments, banks or NGOs. In Jalandhar, the training sessions are mainly handled by the government. All the group members were not present. Only the president along with the secretary of the group was available. The information provided by them is considered as the representative for all the group members. The level of satisfaction was reflecting in their eyes. Most of the villagers feel proud to have their names mentioned in the registers provided once they develop the faith in the system.

CASE VII: *Baba Nirnjan Das Ji SHG*¹³

Location	VPO Tallan, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	April 06, 2007
Category	General Category
Date of Monthly meeting	10 th of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs. 100/- per month per member
Office Bearers	President: Madhubala Secretary: Narinder Cashier: Paramjeet Kaur
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Bank Associated	Bank of Baroda, Tallan Branch Office
Details of the Bank Loan	First Loan: Rs 80,000 from BOB
Counseling	The group is getting the counseling from the staff members of SGFI (Sports Goods Federation of India), an NGO working in Punjab working against child labour in the sports goods industry.

The group is two years old with only five members. As per the guidelines issued by Government of India, SHGs must have at least ten members. The group maintains its records on the registers printed for the purpose and supplied by governments of India. It has its bank account also. Such a group could be formed but will not come under the preview of SGSY scheme of the government. Most of the members depend upon football stitching for their livelihood. The monthly meetings are held every month at the residence of one of the office bearers. The loan of Rs 80,000 was taken from BOB Bank in August, 2008 and paid back in ten monthly installments. The amount of the loan was divided among the five members in the proportion of the ratio decided among them based on their personal needs. All the members spent

¹³ Based on the meeting with the president of the group at her residence as on 5th January, 2010.

the money for the purchase of the annual stock of wheat for their families. The borrowed funds has fulfilled their personal needs for the time being but later on, these group members will find it difficult to repay the funds. In order to avoid the same kind of the system, as it was in under money lenders, it is tried to be ensured that the funds are devoted for some productive work. The credit for promotion and maintenance of the groups in the village goes to the social worker Mr. Dilbagh Rai who is running a football stitching center in the village. The center is owned by him and the poor villagers are provided training for football stitching there. The footballs are send by the manufacturing companies on daily basis. With the whole hearted support available to the groups, the villagers are encouraged to indulge in the activities of micro financing. The groups are claimed to be the best run groups in Punjab. The government is criticized because the groups running under it are either fake or less operative and at times comes at the point of dissolution due to absence of external operational support.

CASE VIII: *Ganga SHG*¹⁴

Location	VPO Kalwan, kartarpur, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	April 01, 2004
Category	BPL Category
Date of Monthly meeting	5 th of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs. 100/- per month per member
Office Bearers	President: Parminder Kaur Secretary: Kamaljeet Kaur Cashier: Harjab Kaur
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Bank Associated	Punjab National Bank, Kartarpur Branch Office
Details of the Bank Loan	First Loan: Rs 50,000 from PNB in Nov, 2004 Second Loan: Rs 2,40,000 from PNB in June, 2008

¹⁴ Based on the remarks given by the group members at Kartarpur as on 6th January, 2010.

Counseling

The group is getting the counseling from the staff members of SGFI (Sports Goods Federation of India), an NGO working in Punjab working against child labour in the sports goods industry.

Five years old group with the member strength to fourteen is well operated throughout its life span. The details of the current financial status of the group are declared in the monthly meetings. The two loans of Rs 50,000 and Rs. 2,40,000 were paid back in time in form of monthly installments. The amount of the loan is utilized for personal needs like opening up of STD, computer shops or cloth shops, buying cattle etc. The major amount of the second loan was collectively utilized for the manufacturing of the surf, detergents or other liquid dish washing materials, phenyl and making up of soft toys, hand-knitted woolens. The finished products were offered for sale occasionally at the exhibitions organized at Jalandhar or Kartarpur. This is one of the groups which are following the real spirit of the micro financing. The researcher has come to know only single group which has invested the borrowed funds in the joint project in the entire Jalandhar District. The name of the group can also be seen in the lists of SHGs, on the website of Ministry of Rural Development, which visited Pragati Maidan, New Delhi last year to exhibit and sell their produce. These groups set an example for the other intended groups intentional to get the financial benefit through the SHGs. The reason behind the success of the group is two fold. One is the cooperation practiced by the group members and the other is the no funding restrain. The group was claimed to be very well coordinated by all its members throughout the life span. But the business propositions did not turn very active in the group due to various reasons. Firstly, the external borrowings are administratively restricted by the banks by creating bureaucratic hurdles. Secondly, the sale of the finished products is a major issue. It could be accepted that there is always a less demand for the local products without extremely superior quality and attractive packaging. Wherever, the government takes the step towards the direction, the exhibitions are organized for facilitating the combined sale of the artistic and other products manufactured by the group members. Due to negligible advertisements in the region, the sale does not turn up and the members have to bear the additional burden of cost of loading and unloading of the produce and the loss of the day's work.

CASE IX: *Sant Ramanand SHG*¹⁵

Location	VPO Tallan, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	13 th August, 2007
Category	Non- BPL (General Category)
Date of Monthly meeting	10 th of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Office Bearers	President: Paramjeet Kaur Secretary: Binder Cashier: Vidya Devi
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Bank Associated	Bank of Baroda, Tallan Branch Office
Details of the Bank Loan	First Loan: Rs 60,000 from BOB as on 12 th Sep ,2008 Second Loan: Rs. 1,00,000 from BOB as on 18 th Feb, 2009.
Total Deposits till date	Rs. 53,000 (approx. till September, 2009)
Counseling	The group is getting the counseling from the staff members of SGFI (Sports Goods Federation of India)

All the fifteen female members of the group are within the age group of 30-50 years. The group has raised two loans from the bank and repaid in time. Most of its members depend upon football stitching for their livelihood. It is well-operated group in the city and hence is not facing any external and internal issues which require the attention of the authorities. The system of micro financing has been favoured by the representative of the group and she has not contributed any suggestions for the study. The internal lending is mostly in the range between Rs. 5,000-10,000 repayable in the ten equal monthly installments. The major portion of external borrowings has been given to one of the group members and was utilized for the marriage of her daughter. The group belongs to the extremely poor class but does not appear in the BPL category. Though the group can raise the additional funds but they do not seem to be very

¹⁵ Based upon the interview at the residence of president of the group as on 31st Jan, 2010 in the village Tallan.

enthusiastic for the same.

CASE X: *Sri Guru Ravi Das SHG*¹⁶

Location	VPO Tallan, Navi Abadi, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	October 23, 2007
Category	Non BPL (General Category)
Date of Monthly meeting	10 th of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Office Bearers	President: Manjeet Kaur Secretary: Sarabjeet Kaur Cashier: Jaswinder Kaur
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Bank Associated	Bank of Baroda, Tallan Branch Office
Details of the Bank Loan	First Loan: Rs 60,000 from BOB as on 21 st June ,2008
Total Deposits till date	Rs. 37,500 (approx. till 31 st Dec, 2009)
Counseling	The group is getting the counseling from the staff members of SGFI and social workers in the village (Sports Goods Federation of India)

The meeting was possible by the efforts of the one of the counselors in the village who is running the center for football stitching in the village at a central space. Most of the villagers are getting their monthly income through football stitching in the center especially the female population. The old group consisting of 15 female members within the age group of 28-50 years is operating well from the last two years. The internal lending ranges from 1,000-10,000 at 2% rate of interest per month. The group has raised a loan which is utilized for personal expenditures such as purchasing wheat, education of children etc. The members of the group also receive demand for the loan from the outsiders also at exorbitantly higher rate of

¹⁶ Based on the views of the group members in the meeting at the village Tallan as on 31st January, 2010

interest, but are not entertained due to security reasons. No specific problems are faced except the delay in the payment of the installments. Most of its members depend upon football stitching for their livelihood. It is well-operated group in the city and hence is not facing any external and internal issues which require the attention of the authorities. The system of micro financing has been favoured by the representative of the group and she has not contributed any suggestions for the study. The internal lending is mostly of Rs. 5,000-10,000 repayable in the ten equal monthly installments. The major portion of external borrowings has been given to one of the group members and was utilized for the marriage of her daughter. The group could be regarded as the success establishing an example for others. Though the weak points in the group are not negligible but the positive points should be planted in each self help group in Punjab.

CASE XI: *Sant Kabir SHG*¹⁷

Location	VPO Tallan, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	February 1, 2007
Category	Non- BPL (General Category)
Date of Monthly meeting	10 th of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Office Bearers	President: Balbir Kaur Secretary: Gurminder Kaur Cashier: Soma Rani
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Bank Associated	Bank of Baroda, Tallan Branch Office
Details of the Bank Loan	No bank loan has yet been raised by the group
Total Deposits till date	Rs. 65,000 (approx. till 31 st Dec, 2009)

Most of the lending is financed through the deposits of the group internally. In terms of external lending, this group is the least active out of the groups surveyed. Even after

¹⁷ Based on the interview with the group members in their monthly meeting as on 10th Jan, 2010 at the Tallan

more than two years of its establishment, it has not availed the credit from the bank. No internal disturbance has been reported within the group. With the huge internal funds accumulated by the group members over the years, they feel no requirement to get involved in the external bank funding. Since the president of the group claimed that they have a business proposition to start up with the bedding business at a small scale only. The group members came up with the idea to purchase only ten to twelve mattresses with few pillows to lend to the villagers at the time of family functions and gatherings at their homes. Till date the proposition was under consideration. The president was ready to take charge of the business on the behalf of the group members. Such plans for small scale businesses are required to get the full fruits of the efforts for micro financing. Providing micro funds for the personal consumption could never raise the income level of the people and they will remain trapped into the clutches of the poverty.

CASE XII: *Swami Sarwan Das Ji SHG*¹⁸

Location	VPO Kandiyana, Adampur, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	January 23, 2008.
Category	Non-BPL (General Category)
Date of Monthly meeting	5 th of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Office Bearers	President: Poonam devi Secretary: Kulwinder Kaur Cashier: Asha Rani
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Bank Associated	State Bank of India, Adampur.
Details of the Bank Loan	No bank loan has yet been raised by the group members
Total Deposits till date	Rs. 45,000 (approx. till 31 st Dec, 2009)

The group consists of fifteen members who are encouraging internal lending with

¹⁸ Based upon the meeting with the group members at the village Kandiyana, Adampur as on 8th Feb, 2010.

the accumulated deposits of the group. The bank loans are not availed off till date. Most of the loans are given in the range of Rs. 2,500 to Rs. 8,000 and almost every member has taken the loan for different reasons. The reason for not availing the external borrowings is not the administrative problems but the main reason is the lack of any investment options in their hands. The need for the loan will arise only when they have some profitable avenue in their hands. The groups must learn some technique of manufacturing, start up with small business with the cooperation of all the group members. There is no limitation on the sources for training. Personally the group members can pay and learn the art of manufacturing the different products. Moreover various training camps are arranged in the district by the NGOs, government or even banks. The problem lies in the effective communication of such training programmes. The opportunities will only generate the requirements for the funds. Most of the groups in Punjab are facing the similar problem. No group member without the additional reward wants to take the headache of learning some new techniques on the behalf of the group members and start up with the new business venture with the condition that reward will be equally shared by all the group members in spite of the additional effort by a few of them.

CASE XIII: *Satnam SHG*¹⁹

Location	VPO Mehmampur, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	24 th November, 2006
Category	Non-BPL (General Category)
Date of Monthly meeting	5 th of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Office Bearers	President: Kulwinder Kaur Secretary: Inderjeet Kaur Cashier: Sonia
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly

¹⁹ Based upon the records of the group members in the meeting at the village Mehmampur at 20th Feb, 2010.

Bank Associated	UCO Bank
Details of the Bank Loan	No bank loan has yet been raised by the group
Total Deposits till date	Rs. 60,000 (approx. till 31 st Dec, 2009)

There are twelve members in the group who have the internal lending as the major source of funding to the personal needs of the group members. The loans are granted in the range of Rs. 1,000-10,000 per loan per member. As similar to the other groups in the line, this group also does not have any different story to describe. The group collects the deposits on or before the date of monthly meeting. All the matters with regard to the progress of the group within the month in terms of deposits, loans and other happenings are discussed among all the members. In the meeting the issues like default in the payment etc. are also discussed and the members found guilty are dealt accordingly. As per the written rules of the group, the members are to pay some nominal amount of penalty and in the extreme cases they are made questionable also in front of the whole group in order to make them feel guilty for the conduct. The group members presented a positive approach towards micro financing and the whole system in the region.

CASE XIV: *Jai Sattan Di SHG*²⁰

Location	VPO Mehmampur, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	24 th Nov, 2006
Category	Non-BPL (General Category)
Date of Monthly meeting	5 th of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Deposit collected	Rs. 65,000 with interest (31 st Jan, 2010)
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Bank Associated	UCO Bank

This group reflected a unique behavior at the time of the interview. At the initial

²⁰ Based upon the views expressed by the members in the meeting at Gadibaksh as on 19th February, 2010.

stages of its incorporation, the group faced various internal problems. But at present the group can narrate its success stories to the other initiators. There are fifteen members in the group now. In the initial years, the cashier of the group misappropriated Rs.8,000 out of the accumulated deposits. Though the village panchayat interfered in the matter but the amount could not be recovered. All the members suffered the loss and now the group is operating well. Like various other groups, this group has also relied mainly to their own funds rather than borrowing from the bank. These matters are sorted out at the attempt of either NGOs in the region or the government representatives. No doubt, the group members suffered at the initial stage but the amount of the loss is recovered with the passage of time through the amount of interest recovered on the amount lend. Now the group is running well and planning to start up with the new options though at the individual levels. The one of the group members wants to complete the construction of the house with the money borrowed from the bank and plans to earn from rent of the same. Another member has the proposal of buying cattle for milking. As per her prediction, there is demand for the milk in the village and she can earn. These small ventures are helpful specially in the cases where the male member of the house is either has expired or not working and the mother need to support the family and pay for the education of the children .

CASE XV: *Dr. B R Ambedkar SHG*²¹

Location	Kandiayana Guruka, Gadibaksh, District Jalandhar.
Category	Non-BPL (General Category)
Date of Formation	30 th July, 2009
Date of Monthly meeting	5 th of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Accumulated Deposits	Rs. 68,400 (approx.)
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Bank Associated	Cooperative Bank

²¹ Based upon the interview with the group members at Gadibaksh as on 19th February, 2010.

Bank loan detailsRs. 1,00,000 (2nd March, 2009)

The group is running well and there are no problems faced that need a special attention by the policy makers. Being the newly formed group, the group members are now settled as the team but have not come out with the business proposition. As the villagers are illiterate and are not very aware of the financial calculations. They take time to learn the system of filling up the deposits register and the other details. Even the cashier who is supposed to maintain the record of every cash inflow and outflow, they are to be guided by the any other existing group, members of NGOs or government officials. Rather sometime they also take the help of the educated children of the village for understanding the record maintenance that is supposed to be maintained in Punjabi language being their mother tongue. The loan already taken by the group is distributed among the group members in the equal proportion. Such amount was utilized for meeting the personal needs of the group members e.g. paying the school fee for their children, meeting the marriage expenses, construction, purchasing cattle and other small expenses which form the part of the daily expense chart of the poor villagers. Unless they are not able to satisfy their basic needs, they will certainly not go for the business propositions.

CASE XVI: *Dr. B R Ambedkar SHG*²²

Location	Gadibaksh, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	11 th January, 2007.
Category	Non- BPL (General Category)
Date of Monthly meeting	5 th of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Office Bearers	President: Raj Pal Secretary: Gyan Pal Cashier: Pradeep Kumar
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly

²² Based on the interview with the group members as on 19th February, 2010 at the village Gadibaksh.

Bank Associated	Cooperative bank
Accumulated deposits	Round about Rs. 70,000
Details of the Bank Loan	Rs. 60,000 (as on 8 th May, 2008)
Total Deposits till date	Rs. 45,000 (approx. till 31 st Dec, 2009)

There are twenty members in the group which is the maximum limit permissible under SGSY scheme. Most of the groups are women groups in the region. This is the only one in this category which has all the male members. This group is also not an exception because it has utilized the bank borrowings for meeting their personal needs. They, too, have not taken any entrepreneurship route for investments. As per the survey conducted and the remarks generated by the officials and the group members, the male groups are not promoted in the region because of the element of trust. The males are considered less trust worthy as compare to eth females. The loans raised by the females are presumed to be more secure as compare to the loan given to a male group. Since the male are more prone to addiction of wines and other such products, the borrowed amount are more likely to be misapplied to the socially destructive practices. Moreover, the uneducated male population does not take much concern of the family who is dependent upon them for their basic needs. These few observed reasons may have promoted the female in the area but this group is very successful in maintaining the cooperation among the group members and getting the loans from the banks.

CASE XVII: *Baba Ji SHG*²³

Location	VPO Kandiyana Guruka , District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	26 th February, 2009
Category	Non-BPL (General Category)
Date of Monthly meeting	5 th of every month
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly

²³ Based upon the meeting with the group members as on 13th March, 2010.

Details of bank Loan No bank loan has yet been taken by the group.

Bank Associated UCO Bank

There are fifteen members in the group. The group is running well till date. Being the newly established group, it has not yet obtained any bank loan and their internal lending is even small due to lesser needs of the group members. The deposits are being collected in time by the cashier and deposited into the bank account immediately after the monthly meeting. All the group members were personally enthusiastic for the growth of their group. Since it is not a new group in the village, the group members are already aware of the various procedures to be adopted for running a successful group. The meeting with the group members also concluded that the group is formed but they don't seem to have the need for external borrowings.

CASE XVIII: *Bheem Rao SHG*²⁴

Location VPO Dhanduwal, Shahkot, District Jalandhar.

Date of Formation 24th November, 2006

Category BPL (General Category)

Date of Monthly meeting 7th of every month

Amount of monthly Deposits Rs 100/- per month per member

Rate of Interest on the loans From members - 2% monthly

Bank Associated Canara Bank

Bank Loan Details **First Loan:** Rs. 25,000

Second Loan: Rs. 2,50,000

Being the older group, all the members are now well managed and cooperative. Though in the beginning, the office bearers faced a few major problems with regard to the non abusive languages used by one of the group members. There are in total twelve members in the group. The member afterwards was excluded from the group by paying off the deposits entitled to him. Now the group is running well since all the deposits are made in time and the lending are made to the group members only. Similar to the other groups, the group members have used their

²⁴ Based upon the interview with the group members at Lallian Kalan as on 2nd April, 2010.

entire borrowing for their personal needs. Though one of the group members have used the amount for purchasing the cattle to sell milk but there is absence of joint pool of funds for the joint entrepreneurial venture. The members are positive for the growth of the group. They positively reacted on asking the growth of the scheme of micro financing in the region. They consider the approach as the answer to the various difficult problems for which the government is unanswered. The scheme could help the villagers living below the poverty line to help themselves with the basic support of government subsidy.

CASE XIX: *Guru Ravi Das SHG*²⁵

Location	Lallian Kalan, West Block, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	13 th July, 2006
Category	BPL (SC Category)
Date of Monthly meeting	10 th of every month at 11:00 pm
Office Bearers	President- Bimla Devi Secretary- Jaswinder Kaur Cashier- Santosh
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Bank Associated	Punjab National Bank, Lambra.
Bank Loan Details	First Loan: Rs. 50,000 Second Loan: Rs. 3,00,000

There are twelve members in the group. Being the older group, all the members are well managed and cooperative. Till date the group is forty six months old which means that the basic deposit of the group members stood at Rs. 4,600 per member but the eye opening statement made by the president of the group is that the interest accumulated over the years exceeds Rs, 25,000 for the entire group. The total funds of the group also increased with amount of the subsidy granted by the government on both the loans. The president of the group felt pride

in describing the success story of her group in front of the office bearers of the other groups of the village. She proudly described that the deposits as well as the amount of the loan is paid back in time by the group members and for the same she need not to demand from any of the group members since she has the responsibility of collecting all the deposits. No one in the group has ever created any problem for her. All the receipts and payments are recorded immediately at the time of the receipt with full signature or the thumb impression of the paying member. Such a practice created a faith in the system because once the register is signed, no one can deny the payment, neither the president nor the member. Once the group turns into a team, the working gets smooth with the mutual understanding of all the group members. the visit to the village Lallian Kalan has become a memorial due to the presence of three group members at the time. All the groups were on the different stages. First group which has completed four years of success start guiding the other initiators in the field. The second group is only six months old and is planning to apply for the revolving fund from the bank. They are unaware on the most of the issues of the micro financing and depend upon the already running group of the village. The third group is the new one and facing the problem of the initial non cooperation of the members. After four months of incorporation of the group, the office bearers want to quit due to the non cooperative attitude of the cashier. The group members of the other two groups were guiding them for sorting out the issues at this stage. The whole scene is a memorable movement because the persons running the system are much convinced with it.

CASE XX: *Sri Guru Ravi Das Shakti SHG*²⁶

Location	Lallian Kalan, West Block, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	10 October, 2009
Category	BPL (SC Category)
Date of Monthly meeting	10 th of every month at 11:00 pm
Office Bearers	President -Bakhsho Secretary - Ranveer Kaur

²⁵ Based upon the views expressed by the group members at Lallian Kalan as on 2nd April, 2010.

²⁶ Based upon the views given by the group members at the meeting at Lallian Kalan as on 2nd April, 2010.

Cashier- Asha Rani

Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Bank Associated	Punjab National Bank, Lambra.
Bank Loan Details	No loan has yet been availed

All the thirteen members of the group are constructed well. The possibility of the delayed payment by some of the members will not be denied. But the solutions are being suggested out of which the reminder in the monthly meeting in front of the Mukh sewika of the block in order to maintain the discipline. The group members are well managed and the president seems to be satisfied with the conduct of all of them. Being new for the system, she requires the assistance at every stage from the outsiders. Her face was filled with the proud while describing the conduct of her group.

CASE XXI: *Sri Shiv Shakti SHG*²⁷

Location	Lallian Kalan, West Block, District Jalandhar.
Date of Formation	10 October, 2009
Category	BPL (SC Category)
Date of Monthly meeting	10 th of every month at 11:00 pm
Office Bearers	Not Available from the records
Amount of monthly Deposits	Rs 100/- per month per member
Rate of Interest on the loans	From members - 2% monthly
Bank Associated	Punjab National Bank, Lambra.
Bank Loan Details	No loan has yet been availed

Being the new group, the members are facing the internal cooperation issues due to misunderstanding and non-supportive attitude. The details of constitution of the group, members, deposits collected at each stage, the internal lending are not recorded at the register

²⁷ Based upon the interview with the group members at Lallian Kalan as on 2nd April, 2010.

specifically designed for the purpose. The cashier was being considered as the culprit in the matter. The researcher fails to meet her but the whole matter appeared to be as the misunderstanding among the office bearers of the group. The matter was being handled by the Mukh Gram Sewika of the village by arranging a meeting with all the group members. The meeting will clarify the deposits collected and the financial status of each group member. Due to non confidence shown by the main office bearers, the last two deposit installments were not given by the group members.

Some Observations Based Upon the Case Studies

Based upon the various groups surveyed, few patterns appear which could contribute to be considered as the universal in nature. The operational methodology, rules governing the group members, the area of the problems, their recommended solutions appear to be similar for all the groups.

- I. All the groups surveyed in the region have the limit of monthly deposits to Rs. 100 per month per member. The amount is deposited in the bank account and withdrawn at the time of payment. Internal lending is promoted by most of the groups which puts a question mark on the system. Is borrowing the difficult or is it the result of ignorance
- II. Proper and detailed information is not conveyed by the BDO/ CDPO workers on time to time basis. There is lack of proper support of any agency, NGO, Government or banks it selves to promote the collateral borrowings.
- III. The government officials have the targets only for formation of the new groups but no responsibility with regard to their maintenance. Hence no physical and other supports are lent by them after the group has been formed on the papers. The illiterate group members themselves have to face the initial internal disturbances and handle out all the administrative hurdles in getting the loan sanctioned from the bank. Most of the time which results into loss of confidence of the members and at last the newly formed group.
- IV. Most of the groups are accumulating their deposits to finance their own personal smaller needs which earlier used to force them to the moneylenders at the exorbitantly higher rates of interest. But the micro financing is not utilized in the true spirit of raising the money from the bank on the collective security of the group and investing in the commonly selected avenue to make revenue out of it.
- V. Most of the groups surveyed have their accounts with the UCO bank. They claim to be satisfied by the treatment provided by the bank officials. Since the technique adopted for the selection of the sample unit is convenience sampling, every unit has the equal chance of being selected. It may be coincidence that the region covered is dominated by UCO bank or it can conclude that the micro financing is being encouraged in the region by the network of remote branches of UCO bank. This could be future research orientation to explore the contribution of the different banks in the growth of SHGs in the region.

- VI. Most of the group members have the number of members more than ten and it is a comfortable number to manage and ensure full cooperation as far as the conduct of meetings, collection of deposits and internal lending are concerned.
- VII. Most of the borrowed funds are utilized for meeting the personal needs of the poor group members rather than channelizing them for the intended entrepreneurial tasks. The true spirit of micro financing is dumped by the real practice followed by the financially deficient villagers.
- VIII. Most of the groups have their rule book which is binding on every group member. There are penalties for absence from the monthly group meeting, delay in the payment of monthly deposit and the delay in the repayment of the borrowed external or internal funds maximum to the extent of Rs. 5 per member per default.

It is concluded that the groups in the Jalandhar district are similar to various respects such as amount of deposits, repayment pattern, utilization of borrowed funds, minimum number of members and reach by the government officers etc. The groups are similar with the exception of the amount borrowed from the bank. Few of the groups have borrowed heavily from the banks and utilized the amount for the personal funding and there are also various other groups which have not raised even a rupee from the bank and operating with their personal accumulated deposits in the group.

CHAPTER V

**FACTS ABOUT SHGs AND
MICRO FINANCING IN
JALANDHAR DISTRICT**

FACTS ABOUT SHGs AND MICRO FINANCING IN JALANDHAR DISTRICT

The micro financing is at the development stage in Jalandhar city. In the initial years of its launch, the scheme was overwhelmed by the residents of the district. Due to the organized and dedicated efforts by the government departments and the NGOs operating in the region, the micro financing has received wider coverage in the region. The awareness campaigns and official visits to the villages in the district were organized on continuous basis in order to generate the confidence of the poor and illiterate villagers in the mechanism. Since in the beginning years it was hard to convince and form the groups but in the passage of two to three years, the number was encouraging for future growth of the system. The year 2005-06 could be declared as the peak year for the growth of micro financing in Jalandhar district. In the following years it faced the stagnation stage with the alarming decline in the overall number of SHGs in the region along with the low rate of disbursements in spite of the availability of huge funds at the disposal of the government for SHGs and micro financing. The present study could claim that the district definitely has not reached the condition of satiety in terms of funds requirements by the poor villagers who still need money for their daily routines as well as micro entrepreneurial projects. Thus the possible reasons for such a non-justifiable decline need to be explored. The possible reasons could be two-phased. Firstly, there may be the poor efforts by the officials assigned with the duty of forming and maintaining the SHGs in the district or secondly, the scheme failed to develop the confidence in the poor villagers. Poor response based on the experience of the existing group members in the villages may de-motivate the others to initialize with the micro financing.

As per the data obtained by BDO and CDPO Office, the following scenario of micro financing appeared in the district. There is variation in the distribution of groups and funds over the years and over the ten blocks existing in the city.

In Figur-1, the bell-shaped figure reflects that the number of SHGs has increased as well as decreased over the years. Initially, the number of SHGs raised showing the rising trend in the micro financing movements in the district. After reaching at the comfortable level of 117 groups in all the blocks in the year 2005-06, it started falling to the alarming lower level. The

research tried to find out the possible reasons for it. One of the major is the lack of enthusiasm among the people in the unexplored area due to neagtive motivation by the existing group members and absence of remarkable change in the standard of living of the villagres who are already the part of the system. The blame could also be put on the shoulders of the officers /representative of the government in the region or decline in the efforts of the official hands etc.

Figure 1: SHGs in BPL category in Jalandhar District 1-4-1999.

Figure 2: Block-wise Distribution of SHGs in BPL category in Jalandhar

As the Figure-2 describes, there is lesser variation in the number of SHGs in the

different blocks in the city. Except a few blocks, like Lohian, all the other blocks are holding the similar contribution for financial inclusion of the poor in the region. All the regions are associated by the Gram sevikas from BDO Office and the representatives from the CDPO Office, Jalandhar district. One block is assigned to one office bearer, for which she is personally responsible for effectively carrying on the financial inclusion. They should encourage the development of the new groups in the region and for maintaining the existing ones. They are also provided with the monthly targets for creating the new groups in their blocks.

Figure 3: Loans disbursed in the Jalandhar District since 1-4-1999.

Figure-3 explains that similar to the pattern shown by the inclusion of new SHGs over the years, the amount of the loan is also facing a downward trend after being at the peak of Rs.167.51 lakhs in the single year 2005-06 in the district. This is the huge amount but it failed to maintain the satisfactory level in the following years. From the very next year, the lending in the region is negligible. Can we assume that all the potential demands for the funds in the city have been met in the due course? As found in the present study, people still need funds for the initializing the small entrepreneurial projects like starting up with the mobile shops, glossary shops and cloth shops etc. Still the level of funds released is declining that is creating a huge gap in the demand and supply in the region.

Figure-4 reflects that the loans have been provided disproportionately in the

region. Block Nurmahal has received Rs.83.95 lakhs (18% of the total disbursed funds) for 53 groups over the entire period in comparison to Lohian receiving only Rs.0.25 lakhs (0% of the total funds disbursed) for 15 groups. The reason could be the lack of knowledge and potential in the region for micro financing or the lack of efforts on the part of Government administration.

Figure 4: Block-wise Loans disbursed in Jalandhar District

Figure 5: Number of SHGs passing the grades since 1-04-1999

Figure-5 reflects that the number of SHGs passing Grade II is very as compare to the total number of groups. Less than fifty percent of the groups are able to be benefited by the efforts targeted for financial inclusion of the poor population. Most of the groups are able to get

the loan of the nominal amount at the stage of six months of establishment of the group. SGSY scheme avails the real benefit with the subsidy provided in the second lending released after passing the grade II by the group. Till date, there are only 133 groups out of the total of 432 which have actually availed the basic loan at the stage II.

Figure 6: Average Rate of disbursements per SHG since 1-04-1999

The average rate of disbursement of the loan is declining over the years as shown in Fig-6. Initially it was around four lakh rupees per group but now it is just four thousand per group. In the last years, it is even negligible. The reason is the decline in the number of groups in the region along with the lesser realise of the funds by the government. The gap between the number of groups and the rate of disbursements is more visible in the Fig 7. The rate with which the number of the groups are rising is followed by the disbursements made over the years to SHGs. But in the downward trend of the groups, the disbursements declined first as compare to the number of SHGs. Can it conclude that the decline in the number of SHGs is the outcome of the decline in the availability of the funds at its disposal? With such a huge decline in the funds, the number of the groups also started falling with the passage of time.

As it clear from the Figure-7, if the rate of disbursements is compared with the number of Self-Help Groups, we find an asymmetrical pattern. As the disbursements started showing an increasing trend, the number of SHGs increased very slowly and not in the line with the rate at which the funds are available. At the later stage, when the number of SHGs shown a

rising trend, the lesser funds were realized in comparison to the requirement of the sector.

Figure 7: Comparison between the number of SHGs and Disbursements

As from the above analysis of the data, it is concluded that though the SHGs have shown a rising trend in the initial years. But the current condition demands an immediate action by the government to prevent the system to be declared as the complete failure in Punjab blaming the cultural disparity and financial soundness of the villagers.

Figure 8: Non-BPL groups (under CDPO) engaged in the economic activity

It will be wrong to say that the system is not enough supported by the allocation of the funds on the part of the government. There is huge gap between the funds available and disbursed. A joint effort is required from all the parties concerned with the implimenattion.

As per the data obtained from the records of CDPO Office, the Non- BPL groups engaged in the economic activity are a few. In some of the regions not even a single group is found which is investing the borrowed funds in the business ventures. The groups are utilizing the borrowed funds for their personal consumption which kills the true spirit of micro financing. The group members are further trapped into poverty circle with the over expenditure on the items which are not generating income in the long run in order to help them to repay the borrowed money.

The usual pattern reflected under the data is the sharp increase in SHGs and tremendous growth of micro financing in the region in the span of eight to ten years. But the decline is even steeper in the number of SHGs in the district affecting the amount disbursed to the small business ventures. The rate of disbursement per group also declined due to the decrease in the funds borrowed by the groups. The research attempted to diagnose the reasons for such a worse situation. The conclusion blames the system as well as the group members. Firstly, the corruption and other administrative hurdles limits the approach to the deserving needy class of the society. Secondly, the borrowed funds are not properly channelized into profitable business ventures due to which the standard of living of the people did not reflected a remarkable change. Thus the mechanism failed to make a drastic change in the village life.

CHAPTER-VI

FINDINGS

FINDINGS

The Bharat Microfinance Report - Quick Data (2009) reveals that Indian microfinance has reached out to 86.2 million clients and the portfolio outstanding of Rs. 351 billion including MFI channel actual data and SBLP (Self help groups-Bank linkage programme) estimated data for March 2009. Out of this MFI channel client outreach has grown at 60 per cent in 2009 against 41 per cent in 2008.²⁸

“No doubts, India is one of the dynamic microfinance markets in the World”

-Jennifer Meehan, CEO, Asia region for Grameen foundation (**Meehan, 2009**)

It is at a much larger scale and appear as the major step in reducing poverty. Last few years have been Microfinance emerged as a noble substitute for informal credit and an effective and powerful instrument for poverty reduction among people who are economically active but financially constrained and vulnerable in various countries (**Varman, 2008**). As per Microfinance Information Exchange, Inc. (MIX) 2006-07 benchmark data, MFIs across the globe raised the capital from the various sources that includes 36.2% from borrowings, 35.8% from deposits, 15.5% from equity, 9.9% from debt including concessionary loans and compulsory savings, and 2.5% from donations. Thus the substantial capital raised by the MFIs was derived from the deposits (**Mohapatra, 2009**).

There are ten blocks in the Jalandhar region and each block is assisted by a single representative from BDO and CDPO each. The management of more than 1600 groups in the District by a few government executives is not a possible task provided the whole structure is not compatible for growth of Self help groups. The average coverage of each member is sixty groups segregated at the different villages in the city. They are not able to assist them at each step of getting the accounts, loans and subsidies, to guide them for deciding their plan of action for utilising their borrowings and supervising their activities on the regular basis. On the most they, themselves, are expected to visit the new villages to explore the possibilities of new Self help groups there. The villagers are mostly unapproachable for the Government representatives due to the constraints on both the sides. It is hard for the representatives to approach the villagers at the

²⁸The Bharat Microfinance Report – Quick Data 2009, Microfinance India, July 15, 2009; URL:

far-flung regions telephonically because most of the groups are not telephonically approachable and on the other side they are not provided with any of the transportation and telephone facilities. They, at the most, approach the village sarpanch for creating the awareness in the village and all the remaining result depend upon the cooperation of the village sarpanch.

The other support system is MFI which is perceived as the non-professional organization i.e. unfit to invest in. In Punjab, there is negligible existence of any MFI specifically designed and maintained for the promotion of micro financing in the region as per the demand of the NRI as well as agriculture-based families. Commercial banks don't have micro financing & entertaining Self help groups in the remote regions as their primary operation. Being the profit-oriented setups, banks neither possess the relevant infrastructure of branches with the remote access nor try to develop due to limited margins, unsuitable workforce and lack of expertise in the area. In Jalandhar also private commercial banks try to avoid the group bank accounts and don't provide the funds without the security. The source of funds for MFIs varies within the industry. MFIs in India often try to imitate the successful models in the other countries. MFIs need to be more innovative and region-specific. It requires the adoption of agricultural microfinance methodologies which will provide them the competitive edge for reaching the poor in the far flung areas where the commercial banks have the nominal coverage. Poor ran from the pole to the pillar in order to arrange the sufficient funds for their operations. MFIs are often not perceived as the most professional organizations as the big industrial houses and the commercial banks are. In reality they suffer from the limitations of the limited management capacity, Institutional inefficiencies etc. As a result MFIs find it difficult to arrange the loans and obtain the other financial incentives and support from the financial institutions. MFIs are not able to give a drastic change in the rural India. These days MFIs in some of the lesser developed states of India are facing the criticism due to unsuccessful models followed. The products failed to meet the specific local demands. The people fail to trust the system due to various factors which are mostly attributed to the MFIs in India.

The second side of the picture is also not very encouraging. The bottom level is not aware of this innovative financial option. Few thinkers in the field are negative for the growth of the micro financing in the northern regions of India because in the rural areas, the male

dominant society prevents the women to step out of the house and form the group and in the urban areas there is no homogeneity in the society as well as the system of trust and honour on which the foundations of social security is built. The basic limitation is the dependence of the women population on the males of their families. Self help group mission has been made successful in states like Gujarat mainly due to female population initiatives. In Punjab males hold the major decision power in the family especially in the poor illiterate families which act as the constraint for establishing and running a group. In various cases the internal mechanism of the groups and chemistry among the group members fails due to the default in the payment of the monthly deposits and borrowed funds. The group leaders must be dominating and influential to punish the evil streams in the groups. But in Punjab specifically in Jalandhar, there are negligible cases found with regard to same. Even the reported cases are sorted out at the group level only and in no case result in the dissolution of the group. But to scale up and really make a difference to those outside the normal banking channels, microfinance institutions need to innovate. The group members are facing various semantic barriers and administrative obstacles since their inception. The poor group members have to compromise with their daily wages to make regular visits to the banks for the approval of the loans. The daily workers are surviving on the day's earnings, the loss of which will force them to starve for the day. The major constraint for the low response rate is the illiteracy level of the people in the rural Punjab. In spite of being the well developed state of India, most of the village population is illiterate or less educated. They fail to understand even the simplified system and trust the scheme offered for their welfare. Due to the involvement of the financial matters in the scheme, they fail to rely upon the Government officials, dedicated members of NGOs etc. who are taking care of the development of villages in Punjab. As quoted by one of the members of effective NGO in Jalandhar, the members even condemn them for wasting their time in describing the important features of schemes. Doubtlessly, at the latter stage the same people are financially upgraded by the system of micro financing and then they promote and encourage others also for investment in the system. One of the major limitations of the group financing is that a single individual, possessing a profit-driven business idea, has not been able to access the bank's financial pool due to the non-availability of the ambitious individuals in his social circle. Moreover due to the lesser social network and various personal constraints, the villagers are not able to fulfill the requirement for the seventy percent BPL (below poverty Line) members as the group members for availing the subsidy

available for the BPL category group. The problem lies in the fact that the financial services are boosted for those who are not even aware of their growth options. Firstly this concept has not been infused in the villages. Secondly wherever this concept has been evolved through the rigorous efforts of the various groups responsible for implementation, the concept is not rightly perceived. Illiterate villagers in Punjab consider it as the Kitty (known as kametti in the local language) by the members of Self help group. Some of the schemes are launched by the Government from time to time for providing relief to the suffering people at the bottom levels due to various natural and manmade disasters. The farmers are given the relief by waiving up their present loans. That has not only harmed the present financial sector in the economy but for the future the farmers are given the incentive for not paying the loans in time and pressurizing the Government for the waivers (**Yunus, 2009**). It could be a good strategy for the collection of the votes but cannot be regarded as the viable financial decision.

Table 1: All India Financial Progress under SGSY since inception i.e. 1.4.1999

(In Rs. Crores)

Items	1999-00	2000-01	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06	Total/ Average
Total Funds Available	1961.97	1608.18	1299.55	1178.13	1214.13	1398.98	1396.1	10057.04
Total Funds Utilized	959.86	1117.94	970.32	921.11	1044.25	1242.196	1239.074	7494.75
%age of Utilization to Funds Available	48.92	69.52	74.67	78.18	86.01	88.79	88.75	66.86

Source: Financial Report issued by ministry of rural development ²⁹

The solution could be the extension of the term of the loan and an elimination of the interest for the remaining period of loan. Out of the various schemes introduced for the promotion of microfinancing, SGSY is the longest and most encouraged one. In Punjab, the scheme is implemented and monitored under DC office but the funds granted for the purpose are not fully utilised.³⁰

There is Non-existence of a well developed and conducive policy environment to

²⁹ URL: <http://rural.nic.in/sgsy/repdis/frametostatnew.asp?id=07> Accessed on December 30, 2009

³⁰ Block wise Progress Report of Self help groups formed /Linked with Bank branches w.e.f. 01.04.1999 to 30.11.2009 as per report generated through ADC Office

prevail into. As put up by Mr. Vikram Akula, SKS Micro Finance, the three key issues that a micro finance institution usually faces are lack of capital, the lack of capacity and the high cost of transaction. These limitations restrict the path of growth for the micro financing in India.³¹ There is the existence of bureaucratic hurdles. In Jalandhar also, the operation of taking the loans, through Self help group schemes from the banks at low rates of interest and lending the same at higher rates of interest to the poor villagers and taking the advantage of their ignorance, is being run silently in the villages. Thus the traditional exploitative money lending activities are now prevailing under the umbrella of Government development schemes. Like it takes a lot of time and labour to set up and run a new branch and the banks are sometimes forced to set and follow such principles, under the political influence, as bench marks for which they are unwilling to give in. Due to the political interference the basic cause of the micro financing campaign has disappeared. The privileged section is served under the Governmental efforts in place of the deserving section of the society. The rates of interest charged are quite high as compare to the other loan products of the banking sector, typically 12 to 30 per cent, mainly on account of the high transaction cost for the average sized loan. More coverage and increased customer base will allow these rates to be reasonable. Banks have the advantage over the MFIs because they can avail the benefit of the large scale and have the better competitive advantage also. The high cost of making small loans, relatively in more frequency to the poor section and without the sufficient collaterals are few main causes because of which banks do not actively participate in the development of the Self help groups and the MFIs. These are not considered the profitable ventures by banks due to the presence of structural rigidities and overheads involved. Like in AP and Karnataka, the banks and MFIs charge 12.5% as the member base is high, whereas the areas the critical mass is yet to be approached, the charge is 15%.³² Indian Bank is charging 11.50% for the short term loans up to 2 lakhs and 12.50% above 2 lakhs.³³ The corruption is expanding in the system from all walks of life. Firstly the impressions of corrupt practices are visible from the Government machinery where the stationery specifically designed for Self help groups are sold over and above the approved concessional prices in order to keep their own margins by government officials. On the other hand, wherever the money lenders or the rich section of the

³¹ <http://shantanudutta.sulekha.com/blog/post/2008/05/the-new-money-plant.htm>

³² Suresh Gurumani, CEO, SKS Microfinance, interviewed by Suneeti Ahuja, 'We are growing....', Micro Finance World, published by Financial Express, India, April 2009, pp 20-22

³³ Sundara Rajan, Chairman, Indian Bank, 'We are concentrating in direct Self help group Bank,', Micro

villages are involved in the group financing, they are utilising the mechanism for their business propositions.

The groups were provided opportunity to exhibit and sell their hand made products in Pragati Maidan in Delhi. The products displayed hand-made winter wears, Punjabi jutti (footwear), gud and shakkar, soft toys, detergents, candles, bed sheets and variety of cloths with the hand embroidery and paintings. They earned a profit in the range of Rs. 15,000-20,000 with the sale of one lakh (approximately). Most preferred items were gud-shakkar and hand woollens. But these opportunities are a few. A group from Jalandhar also participated in the display and sale at Pragati Maidan in Delhi. The main constraint in Punjab is the sale of the finished goods in the region at the reasonable margins. Only a few cases are reported where the contributions made for the joint pool of the group through the monthly deposits or the funds raised through the bank are invested in the joint venture based on the skill set of the group. But the joint produce is not able to fetch the reasonable rate of return to the producers because generally they fail to find the market for their product and secondly the cost of selling exceeds the revenue generated through the sale at the individual level. The constraint arises from the marketing point of view also i.e. packaging and advertisement etc. Due to the local production and the lack of the awareness among the poor villagers, the produce fails to attract the consumer in spite of the good quality and the reasonable pricing. All these problems are responsible for the present state of micro financing in the region. In few of the cases, the data is not readily available but on the reverse side, few of the Government departments the data is even available through the official website of rural ministry of India. The state-wise and district-wise (yearly and monthly) reports are available since the last few years. There are various strategic, institutional and connectivity issues connected with micro financing which needs to be addressed for the growth of sector in Indian economy.

The sincere efforts are being initiated at each level to ensure the development of the mechanism of Self help groups so that the balance in the distribution of the wealth can be achieved. Various new ideas are being discovered and in the process of adoption and implementation by various banks and commercial houses. A variety of products like micro insurance, micro pensions etc. are launched by banks and MFIs to expand the horizon of micro

financing. Mobile banking and Tele-payment arrangements are being made by SKS micro finance. MCIs can establish the tie ups with the educational and health institutes to provide the poor with the better access to the public services (**Woodworth, 2008**). From the state-wise perspective, the state of Punjab is one of the least affected areas in terms of Self help group penetration with only 0-5% coverage on the Indian map as issued by IFMR.³⁴ Jalandhar District (Punjab) consists of 958 villages³⁵, which are divided into ten different blocks based on their geographical locations. As per the reports from DC Office, Jalandhar, there are 453 Self help groups under BPL category³⁶ and more than 1200 groups under Non-BPL category. The records are monthly updated by BDO office, Jalandhar and CDPO Office, Jalandhar for BPL and Non-BPL categories respectively. The CD (Credit-Deposit) ratio in the city is as low as 37.82% as on 31-12-2008³⁷ creating a cause of concern for the administrators. Most of the funds are unutilised which should be channelised for the productive investment proposals. Micro financing is the effective tool to maintain the financial balance in the city with the equal distribution of the income by facilitating the financially ignored section of the society. There are certain NGOs also which are promoting the groups formation in Jalandhar District SGFI (Sports Goods Foundation of India), ATMA (Agricultural Technology Management Agency), Pahal and Satin Creditcare are the few names mentionable with the commanding success in the field. They are encouraging the groups through financial and advisory support. They act as the moral boost for the group members at each step from the formation to the application of the borrowed funds in the productive avenues. They encourage micro financing in the area by distributing the rewards to the most effective groups. It is currently in the process of linking these families with health insurance and pension benefits also. Good recovery rate is the only major booster for the market which is not letting the system to fail. Banks are successful in getting the recovery rate up to hundred percent (approx.) in micro financing. Most of the CEOs of the commercial banks and MFIs have claimed the full recovery rate. The social security plays as the binding in the case of group lending. Moreover the borrowed funds are fetching good return from the business ventures

³⁴ Indian Map- Showing the penetration of micro financing in India, issued by IFMR, accessed on 30th March, 2010, URL:<http://ifmr.ac.in/cmfi/map/>

³⁵District Credit Plan, Jalandhar (Punjab), 2009-10 published by the UCO Bank, lead bank for Jalandhar District., pp 3.

³⁶Block wise Progress Report of Self help groups formed /Linked with Bank branches w.e.f. 01.04.1999 to 30.11.2009 as per the report generated through ADC Office.

³⁷District Credit Plan, Jalandhar (Punjab), 2009-10 published by the UCO Bank, lead bank for Jalandhar District, pp 3.

in which invested by the poor borrowers. They are able to leave with good margins even after paying the high interest rates. A survey conducted by RBI finds that the raising the loans from the MFIs is very easy for the poor. They have the close monitoring towards the system for ensuring that there is no default. MFIs have the good recovery rate. District administrations have the satisfactory views for the functioning of MFIs in their limits (**Ravindranath, 2009**). Only in some selected regions, the default rate is less than one percent, but that is very unpopular. Most of the cases, explored in Jalandhar district, have been quoted as the early payment cases according to the senior officials in the banks. The response given by bank officials and the statements as per NGOs are positive towards the recovery rate of the borrowed funds. The reasons found behind the same are sound financial condition of the members of the group, combined social obligation, linkage of future borrowings with the past recovery record etc. Most of the credit has been availed by the disadvantaged section of the society in India. The proportion of women clients is 80% in the current year. MFIs served 7.7 million clients from SC/ST and minority community background.³⁸ It has facilitated the credit support to the groups which remain away from the organized financial network due to various bottlenecks present in the system. Some of the main challenges include coverage, cost of small value transactions, infrastructure, suitable products, flexibility, weak delivery model for community enterprise and financial management support. In the 2000s, the microfinance industry's objective was to satisfy the unsatisfied demand on successful in developing a commercial microfinance sector in India but several issues remain unattended before the industry will be able to satisfy massive national demand.

As far as the financial health and demographic profile of the region is concerned, there are two categories of the population residing in villages. One which is too rich to bother for the tiny groups and its associated small earnings and the other category is too poor to pay even the monthly deposit amounting to Rs. 50 or maximum to Rs. 100. There is a very less demand and encouragement to the mechanism due to the reason that the people in Punjab are well off. Most of the families are NRIs and even, in most of the families, one of the family members is living abroad and earning very handsomely. Financially they don't require small funds to be borrowed and invested for generating normal return. That is the root cause for all the other

³⁸The Bharat Microfinance Report – Quick Data 2009, Microfinance India, July 15, 2009; URL: <http://www.indiamicrofinance.com/microfinance/microfinance-india/the-bharat-microfinance-report-quick-data->

reasons behind the slow progress of the region. On the other side, the poorest group is hard to reach and difficult to convince for the viable business propositions where they are finding difficult to earn their bread and butter on the routine basis. Most of the families are residing in the villages and are earning their livelihood from the allied activities based upon the agriculture. This profession neither requires a formal training nor a huge capital to be invested into. The micro financing through Self help groups reflects such major benefits which are not felt to be availed by the rural Punjab. If the state of Punjab is compared with the other micro-financing rich states in India, the reason for the success of the mechanism in states like Gujarat is the basic need for funds for financing the business options available with them. In Punjab, people are not much business-oriented and that is why they don't require borrowed money. They prefer to remain un-banked. There are a few groups actively working in Punjab region but those are located at the border areas. Jalandhar district is not witnessing the major growth of micro financing. Though there is huge number of groups in the regions as far as the official records concerned. The groups have heavy borrowings on their accounts but the amount is directed towards the personal needs of the group members rather than on the entrepreneurship projects. There is hardly one group found in the entire district that too with the long list of complaints in their hands blaming the whole structure for the failure of micro financing in the region.

There is a lack of proper implementation mechanism. There are four tehsiles in the District and there is no separate mechanism to specifically deal with the micro financing which can be entrusted the task of developing the new and innovative schemes for the development and ensuring its effective implementation. The employees of central and state Governments who are entrusted with the task of implementing the group financing in the villages are not able to boost the sector much due to their financial constraints and the lack of direct linkage of the financial rewards to the performance. No doubt, they are provided with the monthly targets to form new SHGs in their blocks but their monthly remuneration will not be effected with the level of the target achieved. Since Anganwadi workers, who are in the direct contact with the villagers, themselves belong to the class with the limited resources, they require a reasonable level of pay scales. But they are not on the pay-rolls of the Government and are not regarded as the Central or State Government employees as such. There are less number of

members deployed in each block. Taking an example of Jalandhar West, the allotted seats are one Mukh Sewika assisted by six Gram Sewikas reporting to Mukh Sewika of the block. But at present, only one Mukh Sewika is handling all the 112 villages of the block located at the far-flung areas. Routine visit to one village takes one complete working day. In the month, the effective visits could only be twenty which means that every group has its turn after six months. It is hard to be expected out of the workers of BDO and CDPO to supervise already running groups effectively and put more efforts to form new groups. Micro-finance programs have often been implemented by large banks at government behest and they are least interested since these are not considered profitable avenues. The list of BPL (Below Poverty Line) members had been released in 2002 and has not yet been revised for the last many years. The subsidies are granted on the basis of the said list which is not the replication of the poverty in the region because the list has been finalised by the Government agencies under the political influence in order to satisfy their personal motives. The politics must be separated from the economic criteria. It should be based upon the income range and standard of living of the people and must not be biased upon by the favouritism imposed by the village sarpanch and political party supporters. Various training programs are organised at the Government initiatives under various development schemes. But the approach of such programs remains limited because of the wrong selection of location. People in the remote regions find it difficult to reach in the nearby cities where such training sessions are conducted. For them attending a training session means loss of one day's work in addition to the fare charges to the specified location. It could be financially beneficial for the whole group in the long run but it fails to encourage the single member to spend the traveling expenses from his pocket at present. The hidden cost for availing the subsidy from the government is the cost for the stamp papers which are required for the affidavit to be submitted by all the office bearers of the Self help groups which costs Rs. 500 to each of them. This is the additional financial burden to the group members. The poor farmers and labourers are discouraged due to the initial financial burden before availing the financial assistance. It becomes extremely hard when the families concerned are hand-to-mouth.

The infrastructural base used by the Government for the developing and feeding the Self help groups are the nationalised commercial banks acting as the financial support system in the country. The programs are run, not at the discretion of the banks, but the implementation is forcefully imposed to the existing infrastructure of the commercial banks. They lack the

enthusiasm in the implementation which fails to generate the effectiveness in the system. The existing set up of nationalised banks fail at certain specified regions where the branches are short in number for the effective coverage. It is not binding on the private commercial banks to develop the machinery. That is the reason that the most of the deposits of Self help groups are lying with the nationalised banks. Sometimes, the opening of the group accounts in the banks becomes difficult for the poor and illiterate villagers. The problem becomes complex when the administrative and procedural hurdles are infused in the system by the bank officials. The banks used to avoid the financial services to poor clients due to limited margins. Banks are required to incur substantial costs to manage a client account regardless of the amount involved. For example, the total revenue from delivering one hundred loans worth \$1,000 each will not differ greatly from the revenue that results from delivering one loan of \$100,000. There is fixed cost for processing the loans because of which banks prefer the higher loans over the smaller ones leaving them with higher margins in their hands. There is a break-even point in providing loans or deposits below which banks lose money on each transaction they make. Poor people usually fall below it. There are various procedural limitations like delay in the approval and disbursement of the bank loans. The scheduled banks are under the obligation to entertain the cases under Self help groups, but these group accounts results them higher cost and loss of time. That is the primary reason because of which they create many hurdles in the course of grant and disbursement of the bank loans for the illiterate group members who fail to understand the technical paper formalities. Ultimately, the whole process concluded as the tiresome, loss of effective man day's work and additional financial burden on the poor families. The challenge lies in maintaining the remote branches and making all the information available on time. The rural branches are being setup by the banks for the better reach to the remote areas. With the broadband, no doubt, the problem has been solved to a greater extent but the banks are not able to ensure fully hi-tech branches due to financial constraints. The growth of micro financing sector is badly hampered due to the personalized efforts required by the concerned institution. The collections centers are required in the huge numbers because of the limited lending radius of only two square kilometers. The officer is required to approach all the borrowers personally on daily basis for which he is responsible. Mostly big banks can't afford the routine visits and huge expenses in the scenario where the business is coming to them in the urban areas with the reasonably good returns (Ravindranath, 2009). The problem lies in the recruitment and quality

of service provided by the banks also. The banks try to recruit the local residents as the employees in the branches situated in the far flung areas. These people, though less educated, will be able to understand their inmates and will ensure the efficient and comfortable area. Government and the commercial banks acting as the direct lenders to the mechanism are considered external support for the growth of micro financing in India. There is need for the encouraging environment as well as to let the system take its own pace for growth. A tiny segment of US\$30 billion potential market has been reached in the country so far and this is unlikely to be addressed by MFIs and NGOs alone. Reaching this market requires serious capital, technology and human resources. However, 80% of the financial sector is still controlled by public sector institutions (**Arora, 2009**). The government has not promoted any donor subsidies for the fund providers in the mechanism. Due to unsupportive infrastructural base, the poor MFIs, having least social and business contacts, find it difficult to raise the sufficient funds necessary for the survival. Corruption is prevalent which raises the cost of financial transactions and basic infrastructure and public services are not available which add to the burden on financial firms. The firms do not have any information about the financial status of their clients. The law in India does not support the establishment of the Grameen banks. There is a restriction on the non acceptance of the deposits. Thus the establishments specifically constituted for the promotion of a social cause is always fighting for funds. The work also suffers because their primary target becomes the gathering of the pool of resources than serving the economy. The capacity in India becomes limited on the basis that these organizations can never be self dependent (**Yunus, 2009**). There are various such uncontrollable factors in the path of growth of micro financing. These are Information asymmetry, Inability of the poor to offer collateral, No credit history available for the poorest segment of the society, potential success of enterprises difficult to evaluate, low use of technology, high supervision and other costs, high cash handling costs, poorly functioning, and market and other regulatory issues.

The Positive approach by the banking sector is being injected in the system. The approach towards the Micro financing is changing due to the factor that the banks are desirous of expanding the operations in the rural areas also and they are encouraged due to the inherent features present in the mechanism. The banks have developed the positive views for the MFIs when they practically start working with them. They started considering them as the good business facilitators and correspondents. But the attitude favourable for the growth of MFIs has

not gained much of the strength. The only limiting factor is the increased costs of operations for lending to Self help groups but the increased coverage area can limit this cost also. Banks are providing the loans without the guarantee and requirements for the saving bank account by the banks, no prepayment and foreclosure charges for Self help groups, discounted rates of interest for Self help groups for agriculture and allied activities. The Government officers in BDO office and the CDPO office or the members of NGOs have to facilitate. Operational hassles can be removed by creating the awareness and trust among the illiterate and scared villagers who are not able to understand the conceptual base of the scheme and they don't pay weightage due to Government driven scheme, based on the historical experience of poor implementation part of Government initiated schemes. These activities confirms the general perception with the people that bank-based remittances are costly, time consuming and inconvenient.

SKS has pilot running with Unilever Ltd. for supplying the water purifying system, has tied up with Nokia and Airtel to provide the mobile sets and solar lights in the villages by financing the price. Various initiatives are being launched by different banks and MFIs for financial inclusion of the rural India e.g. Zero balance accounts in villages, Credit cards with the facility to withdraw from the rural branches based upto the sanctioned limit, rural mobile ATM. The Self help group members along with the members of NGOs from Jalandhar visited Gujarat and other landmark states to learn the best approach for micro financing. These efforts could facilitate the members to drive management tools from the well known system which could be reflected in the villages of Punjab altered as per the requirements of Punjabi culture and customs.

CHAPTER VII

**CONCLUSIONS AND
SUGGESTIONS**

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Micro financing plays an important role in fighting the multi-dimensional aspects of poverty. Micro financing is also a means for self-empowerment. It enables the poor, especially the women, to become the economic agents of change- they increase incomes, becomes business owners and reduce their vulnerability to external shocks (illness, weather etc.).

- I.** It is very difficult to convince the poor and uneducated villagers to form the group to collect monthly deposits. Moreover the female groups are promoted in the region where the females are subject to various restrictions in the male dominated society. They are not supposed to move out of the house, talk to the men in the society. In such a scenario, expecting them to conduct monthly meetings, lead a team of ten to twenty, visit the banks and talking to the officers of banks, NGOs and government representatives is much beyond the practice. The persons responsible for the implementation have rightly described the situation in their own words. During the survey also the researcher happened to meet various untrustworthy husbands and in-laws who expect their daughter in law to be under the shadow of their dominance.
- II.** Already existing groups do not promote the external borrowing due to ignorance, inconvenience, distrust on the group members, fear of delay or non-payment of the bank loan on their part and the administrative delays, bureaucratic hurdles and non-supportive attitude on the part of banks, government and NGOs. Wherever the funds are borrowed from the banks, the group members do not look beyond their personal needs and hence spend the loan in parts by distributing among all the group members. They never explored the business ventures in order to raise their income. Most of the groups visited are investing in the system considering it as a deposit pool like another bank account, nothing additional to it.
- III.** The records showing the total of SHGs in the district around 1600 is doubted by the NGOs in the region. It is also common saying that the new groups are formed out of the members of the existing groups with a new name and a new formation date in order to meet up the targets by the government representatives. The fact could only be clear if all the groups could be surveyed.
- IV.** All of the groups surveyed have their bank accounts with the nationalized banks who are supposed to fulfill their targets for facilitating a particular scheme. The private banks are not

the active partner for micro financing in Jalandhar. No SHG has its account with a private bank. As per the records of the UCO bank, lead bank in Jalandhar district, only the nationalized banks are facilitating micro financing in Jalandhar.

V. In the recent times, micro financing is bending down towards the technology-oriented system which has facilitated the quick access for the poor, effective distribution and reporting system, correct monitoring but still the effectiveness of the government machinery can be questioned for the reach to the deserving ones. Composite handheld devices; simputers; PDAs; programmed mobiles and *Tijori* micro deposit machines are a few examples worth mentioning which are reshaping the system. A structured set of financial products from FINO have been developed that MFIs can offer to end customers. The products are simple to use and have brand names like *Tijori* (a safe, or locker) and *Tatkal* (prompt, or instant) that the end customers can easily understand and relate to. The delivery channels allow user transaction to be completed online as well as offline, using a simple point of transaction (POT) device and a smart card that every customer is issued. The smart cards are used for storing demographic and financial information about the user, and also contain the user's fingerprint image which is used for authentication.

The emerging conclusions of the study orient towards the key themes of (1) lack of financial viability across much of the Indian rural credit system (2) continuing financial exclusion of many poor people and (3) the need of poor people for flexible, easy to access financial services which protect against risk. The poorer people are, the greater the damage that is done by any declines in assets or income and the greater the need for financial services of a type which will protect the household's livelihood rather than promote it at the cost, perhaps, of greater financial and possibly physical vulnerability.

The essential for the better and effective service, wider reach and growth of the welfare mechanism is the joint effort of all the parties concerned. The mechanism, itself, is very strong and demands no further improvements but still the benefits are not being extended to the poor and deserving population and hence not been able to eradicate poverty from its routes. There are different parties responsible for the promotion of micro financing in the region. All the parties need to pay attention to certain issues creating continuous hindrance in the path of financial inclusion.

It should be considered as the collective moral responsibility by all the parties

directly or indirectly concerned with the policy framing and implementation of the micro financing system. At the level of central decision making, the whole mechanism needs complete restructuring. A separate regulatory agency designed specifically to cater the needs of the sector is recommended at the present stage of growth. There should be a separate regulatory authority for MFIs, distinguished in character from that for the commercial banks. The regulatory authority for MFIs should evolve guidelines keeping in view the objectives of social-economic development of the poor (**Sharma, 2009**). A national level Self-Help Group Federation is required for effective implementation. This issue always waited for the approval but failed due to lack of professionalism and political interference. The factors like cost efficiency, democratic government and almost hundred percent rate of recovery also failed to develop the interest in the masses. The local and national governments also have an important role to play in ensuring the growth and improvement of micro finance. The state wise groups could also be formed with the primary responsibility of developing the support system with the Self-Help Groups and NGOs operated at the route level actually facing with the shortcomings in the system. This will facilitate them to pick up the areas of the improvements. The policy environment could be made more supportive and to clear up misperceptions. There should not be any regulations on the interest rate. It should be a self-guiding mechanism based on the supply and demand conditions in the market. The efforts should rather be directed towards making the interest rates lower by increasing the customer base, establishing a strong chain among the banks, MFIs and the Self-Help Groups and increasing the level of competition in this market. There should not be any scope for individual profits in MFIs. All the profits should be reinvested for meeting the costs of the transactions and for the growth in the long run. A central authority for planning and monitoring is required. An audit committee of all the MFIs and Banks must be constituted. The committee should not have the members of the management and should meet with the external auditors at least once a year to review the issues of the concern. The MFIs can develop their own score card of social and financial indicators to be tracked by the board over the period of time. The representatives of the serving institutes should be present in the remote villages to listen, attend and innovate for the advantage of the people last in the row. That can only make their efforts more socially responsive. The partnering with Self-Help Groups and MFIs with reasonable cost of funding by the commercial banks has been seen as a more optimal approach till now. There should be effective machinery which could ensure the proper monitoring of the

flow of disbursed funds. There exists the proper department for monitoring but that need to ensure that the end use must be for creating assets and sources of incomes rather than wasteful consumption. The follow up can be made by the parties in the direct contact with the beneficiaries. The requisite stationary for the administration of the group e.g. registers, stamp papers and revenue stamps must be available at the block level so that they need not to spent time and money at the cost of their day's work lost. The groups must be physically guided by the government employees in the region i.e. Gram Sevikas, Mukh sevikas, active members of an NGO. The facility of Multi channel access should be provided for remitting the borrowed funds through Bank Branches, door step, multi-lingual call centre and internet etc., which is possible with the effective use of technology. Again in marketing, the Government should develop a common trade mark and promotional strategies for all the micro produce in the region so that the group members can sell under a common brand. There should be well-developed plan for packaging and advertisement of the variety of the produce provided by different groups in the region. A separate agency can be specifically designed and run by the government which can guide and assist Self-Help Groups in the production and sale in the market.

The major initiator and contributory is the commercial bank that has always provided the organized infrastructural base for the implementation at the grass route level. The banks will have to rethink the system as a profitable avenue. The system is required to be developed innovatively based on the models suitable for Indian soils. The banks are required to support the system existing in the rural areas with the association of various public or private hands. The successful collaborations of the commercial banks with MFIs and NGOs, operating at the route level with direct approach to the beneficiaries; can lead to profitable business proposition for the banks. This can provide a larger customer base ahead to their regular users for putting the excess money with the bank into the effective use. Bank will have to accept the reality that it is the large untapped market with almost zero default risk. The institutions directly dealing with the poor families should be collaborated with for the better and safer reach to the soils of the land. Banks need to acquire an appropriate financial technology to service the microenterprise sector, i.e. financial innovations that permit a cost-effective analysis of creditworthiness, the monitoring of a large number of relatively poor clients and the adoption of effective collateral substitutes. Given that microfinance programs differ so radically from traditional banking, banks must recruit and retain a specialized staff to manage these programs.

Issues of recruitment, training, and performance-related incentives require special consideration **(Baydas, Graham, & Valenzuela, 1997)**. Extensive use of technology is required e.g. mobile phone banking and kiosks providing virtual banking services. A lay out of the proposed kiosk that may be opened in the rural areas is given by rural development department of India with the revenue and expenditure estimates. These kiosks may provide various services in addition to providing finance such as issuing necessary certificates, online examination results, driving license, old age pension, BPL survey list, e-mail and matrimonial etc. at the cheapest rates. London based micro-finance expert Malcom Harper commented that India has vast mobile telephone network. Even poor people use mobile phones. Mobiles can be used to transfer small amounts of money needed by poor people with minimal cost. As per the report issued by TRAI, Dec 2009, India has 543.20 million telephone subscribers out of which the majority is wireless subscribers.³⁹ Noting that timely availability of credit is more important for poor than the rate of interest. He added that competition among the micro-finance institutions will take care of the interest rates.⁴⁰ The bank should ensure the convenient and compliant account opening process. Under the survey, most of the problem areas with the banks were associated with the complicated and lengthier account opening process associated with the administrative obstacles created in the area. Micro financing could also be promoted in the villages using the existing networks of Post Offices, well functioning Panchayats, Primary Agriculture Cooperatives Societies (PACS), District Cooperative Banks, Money Lenders etc.

The micro financing should be handled as the business proposition not as the charity. Initially the bulk of the funds required by MFIs for onlending to their clients were met by apex institutions like National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD), SIDBI and Rashtiya Mahila Kosh MFIs should charge interest on the loans to cover their transaction costs. The funds provided for the investments in the local business propositions should be charged adequately so that interest accrued on these funds could be used by MFIs for funding their borrowings from the financial institutions. That will make the system self-fed and not dependent upon the Government and other subsidies etc. MFIs should be allowed to mobilise savings in order to gain the self dependency. Savings could be a very feasible solution particularly in the long run. Various Self-Help Group Federations are being registered but require

³⁹ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_mobile_network_operators_of_India

⁴⁰ <http://www.thehindubusinessline.com/blnus/17201720.htm>, accessed on 12th January, 2010

the freedom for the collection of the deposits from the members also which could be the great source for their funding. The legal framework should be so designed to make the MFIs self-fed institutions. They should not be burdened for looking at the hands of the Government for declaring the subsidies. For encouraging the self dependency in the system, the license fee should be exempted in case the ownership is in the hands of the borrowers. The self dependency of the mechanism will automatically take the growth path as the financing function will not be performed at the cost of efficiency in the service. MFIs should be self sustaining, be allowed to attract deposits, provide insurance and pension fund and should be capacity building as stated by Yunus (Sharma, 2009). The other aspect is that the perceptions towards MFIs need to be revised. The slow growth in micro financing is not the function of the shortcomings present in the mechanism but the perceived inadequate profitability and the insufficient administration in the MFIs. We can't ignore the deficiencies existing in the system which are acting as the major hurdles for the success but the change of attitude of the Government, big financial houses; people at large can surely renovate the system. Due to lack of technical support system MFIs are unable to ensure the satisfied level of services in the rural areas. Credit rating of the MFIs and Self-Help Group Federation can be the solution for generating the confidence. The existing set up of micro financing is lacking the encouragement and financial support from the financial pillars of the country. The credit rating will also facilitate the mobilization of the deposits by the rated MFIs. That could generate the authenticity in the system. Specific credit rating agencies can be assigned the work of rating the MFIs on the basis of internal management, borrowers' base, quantum of lending etc. The innovative and region-specific schemes are required to be developed for the system to be declared as the success in the particular region. MFIs are required to develop the models on the basis of the characteristics and financial needs of the members to be served. The southern parts of the country will certainly differ in terms of the financial requirements, timings of the lending and their paying capacity in comparison to the northern parts of the country. The MFIs should observe the ethical conduct in the business of micro financing which is the mantra for its success. The poor; facing the scarcity of resources, forced to observe the starvations on regular basis and on the most cheated by the money lenders and suffered through the institutional bureaucracy; fails to trust any system specifically designed at the initiative of the Government Thus the MFIs need to gain the confidence of the disadvantaged section of the society by providing the transparent policies and effective utilisation of the funds raised from

them. The other obstacle is the cost factor restricting the generation of earnings which could attract the entrepreneurs in the system. More efforts must be devoted for keeping the transaction cost as low as possible and to reduce the interest rates also.

Transparency and the competition must be encouraged in the field. More involvement of the financial institutions will generate the competition in the poverty funding market which will lead to automatic reduction of the interest rates and will result into customer friendly services. The ultimate benefit will play in the favour of the needy people. The growth of the system is the function of the confidence of the public into the system. Increase in the customer base is the solution for the high cost of funding. A collective effort is required from all the parties either at the planning stage i.e. Government, commercial banks or at the implementation stage i.e. MFIs, Self-Help Groups and the poor who are to be served. Firstly some basic infrastructural support is being provided by the government which will encourage the further private investment in the field.

Some role models can be exemplified and followed by the other program designers in future. BRI (Bank Rakyat Indonesia) designs unique incentive system for their staffs and clients. The BRI staffs receive a bonus based on the profitability and performance of the unit desa in which they work and serve. The profitability and performance of each unit is monitored and assessed along the following five criteria: increase in profit, increase in savings mobilization, increase in KUPEDDES lending (number and amounts), reduction of arrears and long-term loss ratio and improvement in the quality of management and administration (**Hartungi, 2007**). Literature also provides a Business Correspondent (BC) Model where BC can act as the mediator and facilitator in between the bank and Self help group. Linkages of financial literacy and credit counseling centers with the BCs could fast track the financial inclusion. BCs could function as service provider as well as counselor for providing customized financial services Initial security deposit asked by the banks from the BCs could be covered under the credit guarantee fund. For increasing the participation of disadvantaged sections of society, RBI has to simplify the norms and facilitate more people to participate as BCs. These models can be replicated in the different states of India with the regional variations. Customising the products is desirable as per the geographic requirements and providing the incentives to the organizations/institutions working in the remote and difficult areas.

Punjab state is claimed to be one of the well developed and financially sound area

because of the larger number of immigrants from the region. Most of the population constitutes the well-settled families of NRIs who can afford to pay a much higher deposit per month than hundred rupees. The larger portion of the population is the middle class who have the financial needs little higher than the extremely poor class. The people certainly need money but the requirements need more funding per individual. They require financing for running up a mobile repairing shop, grocery shop, their own coaching center and buying a truck for transportation business etc. Micro financing is not promoting higher deposits and funding, which is the main reason because of which the individual financial needs are not being satisfied under Micro financing.

Capacity building of the human resource engaged in the process of providing the financial services. New business ventures and the training are required to make the people professionally well equipped to start and run the small business units successfully. Only the financial boosters will not make the region conducive for the growth of small scale sector. The skill packages of the population required to be supplemented by arranging the various training sessions located at the remote locations in the villages. The awareness with regard to the different scheme, initiated at times by the government, is also poor in the employees responsible for the implementation of these schemes. Effective links like NGOs are required. They overcome various bureaucratic hurdles.

Moreover the real problems are more profound and cannot be tackled solely by capital injections but require fundamental structural changes of the socioeconomic conditions that define informal sector activity and a fuller understanding of the “psyche” of informal sector entrepreneurs. **(Buckley, 1998)**

For the future research, there are various areas which are still remaining unexplored in the region. The conclusion drawn from the story that the number of the SHGs after witnessing as sharp rise slipped downward but the analysis of the data obtained from CDPO office on yearly basis also may reveal a different story. The pattern of BPL and Non-BPL could be analysed in order to guide the government in strategic decision making. The major contributories like banks and NGOs could be analysed for their performance and contribution. Bank-wise and NGO-wise performance analysis could comment upon the contribution of each institution in promoting the micro financing in the region. There is a need to explore the real

truth in order swipe out the bureaucracy in the system to ensure the reach of the funds to the real deserving category in the society.

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ANNEXURES

ANNEXURES

Table 2: Amount of the Loans disbursed in Jalandhar District

Years	Amount of the loans Disbursed (in Lakhs)										Total
	Block 1	Block 2	Block 3	Block 4	Block 5	Block 6	Block 7	Block 8	Block 9	Block 10	
	Jal East	Jal West	Adampur	Bhogpur	Shahkot	Lohian	Phyllaur	Nurmahal	Rurkan Kalan	Nakodar	
1999-2000		4.75									4.75
2000-2001		4.45						2.75			7.2
2001-2002		2.75	22.82	1.15	7.27			3.6			37.59
2002-2003		3.25	21.9	0.25				12			37.4
2003-2004	13.26	9.83	9.25	1.95	0.25	0.25	13.1	5.1	3.5	3.1	59.59
2004-2005	1.6	13.2	3.25	8	37.33		5.4	36.65	23	3	131.43
2005-2006	7.7	11.95		23.7	27.01		33.45	23.85	19.85	20	167.51
2006-2007	0.4	1			1.74		1.2		1.8	1.3	7.44
2007-2008				0.5	0.84				0.8	0.2	2.34
2008-2009											0
2009-2010											0
Total	22.96	51.18	57.22	35.55	74.44	0.25	53.15	83.95	48.95	27.6	455.25

Table 3: Comparison among total number of groups, Pass Grades I and II

Years	Total SHGs	Pass Grade I	Pass Grade II
1999-2000	1	1	1
2000-2001	2	2	2
2001-2002	10	9	9
2002-2003	13	11	10
2003-2004	47	43	24
2004-2005	84	73	46
2005-2006	128	107	41
2006-2007	63	27	0
2007-2008	58	21	0
2008-2009	25	7	0
2009-2010	1	1	0

Table 4: Average Disbursements per group

(in Rs. Lakhs)

Years	Number of SHGs in District	Total Disbursements	Average Disbursements per group
1999-2000	1	4.75	4.75
2000-2001	2	7.2	3.6
2001-2002	10	37.59	3.759
2002-2003	13	37.4	2.876923077
2003-2004	47	59.59	1.26787234
2004-2005	84	131.43	1.564642857
2005-2006	128	167.51	1.308671875
2006-2007	63	7.44	0.118095238
2007-2008	58	2.34	0.040344828
2008-2009	25	0	0
2009-2010	1	0	0

Table 5: Number of SHGs (BPL Category) in Jalandhar District

Years	No. of SHGs										Total
	Block 1	Block 2	Block 3	Block 4	Block 5	Block 6	Block 7	Block 8	Block 9	Block 10	
	Jal East	Jal West	Adampur	Bhogpur	Shahkot	Lohian	Phillaur	Nurmahal	Rurkan Kalan	Nakodar	
1999-2000		1									1
2000-2001		1						1			2
2001-2002		1	4	2	1			1			9
2002-2003		1	5	1				3			10
2003-2004	11	5	11	5	1	1	4	3	1		42
2004-2005	4	10	10	8	12	1	4	14	9		72
2005-2006	9	16	9	17	14	1	22	15	14		117
2006-2007	14	9	2	3	7	2	4	8	8		57
2007-2008	7	16	4	10	3	2	1	7	3		53
2008-2009	1		2	5	2	8	4	1			23
2009-2010									1		1
Total	46	60	47	51	40	15	39	53	36	0	387

Table 6: Non-BPL Groups Engaged in Economic Activity

Block Name	Total SHGs	Groups engaged in economic Activity
Adampur	124	6
Bhogpur	117	104
Jal East	194	51
Jal West	159	6
Jal Urban	19	
Lohian	88	16
Nakodar	136	
Nurmahal	116	
Phillaur	127	6
Rurkan kalan	123	8
Shahkot	122	79